

**BORN, MADE & RECOGNISED:
RETHINKING HOMOSEXUALITY**

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ABSTRACT

Homosexuality is often treated as a modern phenomenon, yet its history stretches past the modern debates construed. This study herein traces the roots of same sex relations across various ancient civilisations particularly pre-colonial Africa; challenging dominant Western framings on the study while highlighting indigenous experiences that predate colonial interventions. It explores the spectrum of cultural, religious, and scientific perspectives that shape contrasting global attitudes—from prohibition in deeply religious countries to acceptance in secular ones.

Findings reveal that African cultural perspectives either diverged from or have been reshaped by colonial rule and contemporary global discourse. Many traditional African societies had fluid and context specific understandings of sexuality, yet colonial laws and missionary ideologies redefined these norms, influencing present day attitudes. This historical shift provides the backdrop for the study's analysis of Ghana's recent Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values Bill, positioning the legislation within broader discussions on human rights, cultural identity, morality, and national self-definition.

Furthermore, the study undertakes the question whether homosexuality is better explained through biological patterns, social construct, or an interplay of both.

This paper adopts a cross disciplinary approach – employing a blend of scientific inquiry, legal study, religious thought, and sociological analysis.

Keywords: Homosexuality, Same Sex, Social Construct, Biological pattern, Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values Bill

KEY TERMS

Homosexuality refers to a romantic or sexual attraction between individuals of the same sex. While once considered a clinical term, modern discourse often prefers “same-sex attraction” or inclusive terms like *LGBTQ+*.

Sexual orientation is the enduring pattern of emotional, romantic, or sexual attraction to others (e.g., heterosexual, homosexual, bisexual). It is distinct from behaviour or identity.

Sexual identity is how individuals define or label their own sexuality, which may or may not align with their orientation or behaviour.

Sexual behaviour involves actual sexual acts and does not necessarily reflect a person’s identity or orientation.

Legal recognition refers to how a legal system protects or regulates sexual orientation, including decriminalisation, anti-discrimination laws, and recognition of same-sex relations.

Social construction sees sexuality as shaped by cultural, historical, and social factors, rather than being purely biological.

Biological essentialism holds that sexual orientation is innate and genetically or hormonally determined.

INAH-3 interstitial nucleus of the anterior hypothalamus

CHAPTER ONE

BACKGROUND

1.1.1 Introduction

Homosexuality has long been a source of intrigue, debate and contention across various disciplines and societies. Put differently, the topic is rarely met with indifference given the array of emotional, psychological, cultural, and religious sentiments it arises.

Notably, homosexuality has often been examined in the frames of biological essentialism vs. social constructionism, whether such is an inherent characteristic in human biology, and if not, a social construct influenced by culture and environment.

1.1.2 Historical Context

This paper, however, commences by addressing homosexuality from a historical standpoint, examining its presence and societal responses across different civilisations.

In Ancient Greece, homosexuality, particularly pederastic relationships, was often viewed as a normative aspect of society, tied to mentorship, education, and social hierarchy.³ Similarly, in Ancient Rome, while homosexual relationships were recognised, they were framed within rigid structures of power and dominance, often reflecting societal norms on masculinity and status.⁴ Contrasting these, Ancient Egyptian records suggest less explicit acknowledgment of homosexuality, although interpretations of texts and art hint at its existence within specific cultural and religious frameworks.⁵

³ Thomas K Hubbard, *Homosexuality in Greece and Rome: A Sourcebook of Basic Documents* (University of California Press 2003) 1–45.

⁴ Craig A Williams, *Roman Homosexuality: Ideologies of Masculinity in Classical Antiquity* (OUP 1999) 19–35.

⁵ Greg Reeder, 'Same-Sex Desire, Conjugal Constructs, and the Tomb of Niankhkhnum and Khnumhotep' (2000) 10 *World Archaeology* 193–200.

In China, historical attitudes towards homosexuality varied significantly over centuries, with early periods such as the Han Dynasty exhibiting a degree of acceptance, as seen in literature and court records, while later eras reflected more restrictive views influenced by Confucian ideals.⁶

These historical insights underscore that societal acceptance or rejection of homosexuality has never been static but rather a dynamic interplay of cultural, religious, and political forces.

1.1.3 Modern Shifts and the Role of Culture

A pivotal aspect of this paper is understanding the shift toward greater acceptance of homosexuality in contemporary times, particularly in liberal, secular societies. For centuries, homosexuality faced significant resistance, often criminalised and pathologized, especially in regions influenced by Abrahamic religions.

However, the late 20th and early 21st centuries have witnessed a marked change, with numerous countries decriminalising homosexuality, legalising same-sex marriage, and enacting anti-discrimination laws.⁷

This shift prompts critical questions: *Why, after millennia of resistance, has there been a growing acceptance in certain regions? Is this shift driven by greater scientific understanding, evolving social norms, or political and economic factors?* The paper explores these questions, juxtaposing the rapid liberalisation of Western societies with the staunch conservatism of many African, Middle Eastern, and Asian nations.

1.1.4 Religion, Culture, and Regional Dichotomies

Religious perspectives are pivotal in shaping societal attitudes toward homosexuality.⁸ The paper reviews historical and contemporary stances of major world religions including Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, and Buddhism alongside indigenous African and Eastern spiritualities. It analyses how

⁶ Bret Hinsch, *Passions of the Cut Sleeve: The Male Homosexual Tradition in China* (University of California Press 1990) 15–42.

⁷ Paula Gerber and others, 'Protecting the Rights of LGBTIQ People Around the World: Beyond Marriage Equality and the Decriminalisation of Homosexuality' (2021) 46 *Alternative Law Journal* 5–12.

⁸ Fatma Zehra, Ayşe Nur and Zeynep E Melike, 'Religion and Attitudes towards Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity' (2023) *Journal of Religion and Community Development* 1–20.

theological interpretations have evolved, often oscillating between outright condemnation, conditional acceptance, and reinterpretation in the face of societal change.

Cultural attitudes are also examined, particularly the dichotomy between Western liberal ideologies, which champion individual rights and freedoms, and the conservatism of many African, Asian, and Middle Eastern societies, where homosexuality is often viewed as a moral transgression or a threat to traditional values.

The paper ties this analysis to Ghana's Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values Bill, a legislative move that has reignited global debates on the intersection of human rights, cultural sovereignty, and morality.

1.1.5 Scientific and Sociological Inquiry

To provide a holistic understanding, the paper incorporates insights from biology to sociology. It evaluates scientific theories about the origins of homosexuality, including genetic, hormonal, and environmental factors, while also interrogating the notion that sexuality is fluid and shaped by societal norms.

Sociologically, the paper considers the impact of globalisation, media, and activism in shaping contemporary attitudes and dismantling traditional taboos surrounding homosexuality.

1.1.6 Relevance to Ghana and Beyond

In anchoring the discussion to Ghana, the paper highlights the cultural, religious, and political dimensions of the nation's approach to homosexuality. By analysing the controversial Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values Bill, the paper situates Ghana within a broader global context, exploring how the intersection of traditional values and external pressures influences legislative and societal outcomes.

This background establishes a foundation for a comprehensive, balanced exploration of homosexuality, weaving historical, religious, cultural, and scientific perspectives into a cohesive narrative. It aims to engage diverse audiences in a critical dialogue about the complexities and nuances of this deeply contested subject.

RESEARCH QUESTION

1.2 Research Question

1. To what extent is homosexuality a socially constructed phenomenon versus a biologically inherent orientation
2. How have historical, religious, and cultural forces shaped its perception and legal treatment in Ghana and globally?

1.2.1 Research Objective

To critically examine whether homosexuality is fundamentally a biologically inherent orientation or a socially constructed identity, and to assess how historical, religious, and cultural narratives have influenced the perception, legal regulation, and societal acceptance of homosexuality, with reference to Ghana within the broader global context.

METHODOLOGY

1.3.1 Methodology

This study employs a qualitative, cross disciplinary research design that integrates historical inquiry, interpretive social science methods, and a structured socio legal analytical framework⁹. The approach is exploratory and interpretivist, seeking to understand how homosexuality has been conceptualised, regulated, and debated across cultural, scientific, religious, and legal domains, with specific attention to African societies a

1.3.2 Research Design

The study utilises a descriptive and analytical framework to explore the topic from multiple perspectives:

⁹ Adam Lindgreen, C Anthony Di Benedetto, Roderick J Brodie and Michel Van Der Borgh, 'How to Undertake Great Cross-Disciplinary Research' (2020) 90 Industrial Marketing Management A1–A5.

- **Historical Analysis:** A review of secondary sources from ancient civilisations such as Greece, Rome, Egypt, and China to trace the evolution of societal attitudes toward homosexuality.
- **Scientific Exploration:** Examination of existing biological and psychological studies to investigate theories on the origins of homosexuality and its classification as either an intrinsic human trait or a social construct.
- **Sociological Perspectives:** Analysis of cultural and societal norms shaping attitudes toward homosexuality, focusing on the dichotomy between liberal and conservative regions.
- **Religious Analysis:** Evaluation of religious texts, doctrines, and historical records to understand the perspectives of major world religions and their evolution over time.
 - a. **Scientific Literature Review**
 - Synthesise findings from genetic, hormonal, and psychological studies to evaluate biological theories about homosexuality.
 - Analyse sociological research on sexuality as a social construct and its interaction with cultural norms.
 - b. **Religious Text and Doctrine Analysis**
 - Interpret key religious texts (e.g., the Bible, Quran, Hindu scriptures teachings) and their passages relating to homosexuality.
 - Analyse historical shifts in religious institutions' positions on homosexuality and their socio-political influences.
 - c. **Sociocultural Case Studies**
 - Conduct case studies on Ghana and other selected nations with contrasting approaches to homosexuality, such as the United States, China, United Kingdom, South Africa and other countries.
 - Analyse media reports, legislative records, and public discourse surrounding Ghana's recent Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values Bill.

1.3.3 Analytical Framework

The data will be analysed using a thematic approach, categorising findings into key themes such as:

- Historical acceptance and rejection of homosexuality.
- Biological versus sociological determinants of sexuality.
- The role of religion and morality in shaping cultural attitudes.
- Regional contrasts between conservative and liberal ideologies.

For the Ghana case study, a comparative analysis will be conducted to juxtapose the country's legislative and cultural stance with global trends.

1.3.4 Ethical Considerations

This research adheres to strict ethical standards to ensure:

- Respect for cultural and religious sensitivities surrounding homosexuality.
- An unbiased and neutral presentation of findings, avoiding advocacy for or against any perspective.
- Confidentiality and informed consent for participants involved in interviews or surveys.

1.3.5 Limitations

Potential limitations include:

- Variability in historical interpretations and scarcity of comprehensive records from ancient civilisations.
- Challenges in obtaining unbiased perspectives, given the polarised nature of the topic.
- Limited access to reliable public opinion data in certain regions due to cultural or political restrictions.

CHAPTER TWO

INTRODUCTION

It would be rather hypocritical to opine that the topical debate of homosexuality is not of collective concern given the noticeable rise of various mechanised schemes. The apparent concern manifests in the saturation of academic literature, increase of media and propaganda, as well as open campaigns across the world. For further emphasis, although the conversation appears to be of vintage length, its relevance is renewed on a frequent basis – a growing apprehension. This conversation traces its origins to the 5th century BC, where the first case of homosexuality was first publicised and critically acclaimed¹⁰. Subsequently, the phenomena became more and more common as humanity continued to develop, resurfacing in the 14th century and finally becoming controversial in the 19th century.¹¹

2.2 Controversy of Homosexuality and The Pillars of Society

It has often been said that the law is to adapt to changing times, thus, metamorphose in respect to the ever-changing dynamics of human existence.¹² However, question remains as to whether newer lifestyle adaptations must be the sole basis in determining the scope of law, or instead, whether the concerns and sentiments of history must be diluted to satisfy the new terrain of life, modifications and diversions of what history recognises as right or wrong.

Although homosexuality has often been tied to the topical debate of morality and ethical conscience as the pivotal driver of the conversation¹³, it appears that the argument extends to other apprehensions of science and human existence.¹⁴

¹⁰ Richard J Hoffman, 'Some Cultural Aspects of Greek Male Homosexuality' (1980) 5 *Journal of Homosexuality* 217–226.

¹¹ Jeffrey Weeks, "'Sins and Diseases": Some Notes on Homosexuality in the Nineteenth Century' (1977) 1 *History Workshop* 1–15.

¹² *Brown v Board of Education of Topeka* 347 U.S. 483 (1954) where the court suggested that the social and governmental changes that occurred within the 19th and early 20th centuries were to be taken into consideration. It suggested that we must "consider public education in light of its full development and its present place in American life throughout the Nation"; Chemerinsky, Erwin *Constitutional Law: Principles and Policies* (2019) (6th ed) New York: Wolters Kluwer. This is also reflected in the case of *Plessy v Ferguson*, 163 U.S 537 (1896). The Ghanaian case of *Tuffour v Attorney General* [1980] GLR 637 suggests that the Constitution is a living organism capable of growth.

¹³ Michael J Sandel, 'Moral Argument and Liberal Toleration: Abortion and Homosexuality' (1989) 77 *California Law Review* 521.

¹⁴ Jennifer Terry, *An American Obsession: Science, Medicine, and Homosexuality in Modern Society* (University of Chicago Press 2010).

This segment, given the above, shall account for the pillars of society and their influence on the general discussion on homosexuality.

2.2.1 Religion

Religion is without doubt one of the most influential pillars of society in setting societal attitudes.¹⁵ For further emphasis, the religious belief system of a society throws light on the lenses through which the world must be viewed, thus, religion dictates what society must accept and reject.¹⁶

2.2.1.1 Judaism

The authors observe that Judaism, like many other religions treats homosexuality with hostility.¹⁷ Substantial attention has been spent on drawing an ideal sexuality and¹⁸ veering off such permissible ideal is labelled a grave sin as it offends divine doctrine. The resentment towards homosexuality within this religious culture stems from the notion that the semen is unclean – a source of contamination and the only place it could be deposited is in a vagina.¹⁹

*And if a man's seed of copulation go out from him, then he shall wash all his flesh in water, and be unclean until the evening. And every garment, and every skin, whereupon is the seed of copulation, shall be washed with water, and be unclean until the evening.*²⁰

Furthermore, in Judaism, there was a sound belief that the responsibility of procreation applied to only males.²¹ Semen was the key to conception, and women supplied little to procreation except a suitable environment to the new being for growth.²² By implication if a woman engaged in lesbian contacts with another woman, little sin was involved, and although lesbianism was occasionally

Vern L Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History (From Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation)* (Hawthorn Books 1979) 11.:
Employment Division v Smith 494 U.S 872 (1990) where influence of religion in law was examined. The United States Supreme Court addressed the balance between religious freedom and state laws, projecting that the impact of religion in law-making : where Justice Antonin Scalia (Majority) “We have never held that an individual’s religious beliefs excuse him from compliance with an otherwise valid law prohibiting conduct that the State is free to regulate.”

¹⁶Jack Nelson-Pallmeyer, *Is Religion Killing Us?* (Fortress Press 2015) 1–92.

¹⁷ Lilith Roggemans, Bram Spruyt, Filip Van Droogenbroeck and Gil Keppens, ‘Religion and Negative Attitudes towards Homosexuals: An Analysis of Urban Young People’ (2015) 23 *Young* 254–276.

¹⁸ Judith R Baskin, *Jewish Private Life: Gender, Marriage and the Lives of Women* (2010) 357–380.

¹⁹ Talli Y Rosenbaum, *Women and Her Judaism* (Jerusalem, Israel 2012)

²⁰ Plato, *Symposium* 191E–192D (WRM Lamb tr, William Heinemann 1953)

²¹ Ibid

²² Ibid

equated with harlotry, few prohibitions were put on the private association of one woman with another; the subject of homosexual relations between women was generally ignored,²³ lesbianism was “apparitional” present but socially invisible.²⁴

2.2.1.2 Christianity

Similarly, in Christian culture, the story of Onan is an indication of the impure nature of emissions and the recognition of the vagina as the only depository.²⁵

Onan was asked by Judah to marry his brother’s wife and raise the children of his brother. Onan knew that he was not to have intercourse with his brother’s wife, thus, he spilled his semen on the ground during intercourse. The Lord was displeased with this act, so he slew him (emphasis ours)

This passage is seen as justification for the condemnation of not only contraception but of masturbation and homosexuality since these activities defy sexual religious values and ultimately procreation.²⁶ It may be correctly observed that religion views this as a violation to divine instruction and even so, a threat to natural values on procreation.

Again, the earliest specific mention of homosexuality in the Bible is found in a portion of the Holiness Code preserved in Leviticus²⁷, “*Thou shalt not lie with mankind as with womankind: it is an abomination,*”²⁸ this goes on to say “*If a man also lie with mankind, as he lieth with a woman, both of them have committed an abomination: they shall surely be put to death; and their blood shall be upon them.*”²⁹

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Terry Castle, *The Apparitional Lesbian: Female Homosexuality and Modern Culture* (Columbia University Press 1993) 1–30.

²⁵ Vern L Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History (From Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation)* 18.

²⁶ Ibid

²⁷ Lucian, *Dialogues of the Courtesans* (MDM MacLeod tr, William Heinemann 1961).

²⁸ Leviticus 18 :22

²⁹ ADC Peterson, *A Hundred Years of Education* (Vollmer Books 1962) quoting Leviticus 20:13.

Further evidence of protest against homosexuality in Christian doctrine lies in the story of Sodom and Gomorrah, where the term "sodomy," was then popularised.³⁰ This has served as the most significant of the biblical condemnations.³¹

The story suggests the vow to destroy all of Sodom and other cities of the plain due to their immorality which mainly stemmed from the practice of homosexuality.³² The Hebrew word *yadha* ("to know") is interpreted as intercourse or in a social sense to be acquainted.³³ The plot of the story follows the great destruction of the cities another religious symbolism of the grave displeasure of God with these practices.³⁴

It has been reasoned that, men and women are sexual creatures, but only for the purposes of procreation, and sex is permissible only in marriage where children are hoped-for as the end product.³⁵ All other kinds of intercourse were evil.³⁶ Some acts were less evil than others.³⁷ Simple fornication was a sin, but since children might as well result from it, it was much less a sin than sodomy or lesbianism.³⁸

In modern slang "blowjobs" or properly so called, "fellatio"³⁹ was also condemned, as was all intercourse in which the woman was not underneath the man and which did not involve the insertion of a penis in a vagina.⁴⁰ These teachings about sex were inculcated into the Christian culture through stories, illustrations (paintings, drawings, etc.), philosophical treaties, and particularly the development of the penance.⁴¹

³⁰ Vern L Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History (From Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation)* 19.

³¹ *Ibid*

³² CS Lewis, *Surprised by Joy: The Shape of My Early Life* (Harcourt Brace 1955) 88–99

³³ Brian Reade, *Sexual Heretics: Male Homosexuality in English Literature from 1850 to 1900* (Coward-McCann 1970).

³⁴ Vern L Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History (From Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation)* 20; Genesis 18–19.; The story of Sodom and Gomorrah is found in Genesis 18-19 in the Bible. These cities, located in the plain of Jordan, were infamous for their wickedness. According to the biblical account, God revealed to Abraham that He intended to destroy the cities due to their extreme sinfulness. Abraham pleaded with God to spare them if righteous people could be found, and God agreed to withhold judgment if at least ten righteous individuals were present. Two angels, disguised as men, arrived in Sodom and were hosted by Lot, Abraham's nephew. That night, the men of the city surrounded Lot's house and demanded to assault the visitors. In response, the angels struck the aggressors with blindness and warned Lot and his family to flee before the city's destruction. At dawn, Lot, his wife, and two daughters were led out of Sodom, but his wife disobeyed God's command by looking back and was turned into a pillar of salt.

³⁵ *Ibid*, pp 26

³⁶ *Ibid*

³⁷ *Ibid*

³⁸ *Ibid*

³⁹ Fellatio, also referred to as fellation or, in slang terms, as a blowjob, BJ, giving head, or sucking off, is a sexual act involving the oral stimulation of a penis. This act can also include oral stimulation of the scrotum, which may also be described as fellatio or, informally, as teabagging, fellation". Merriam-Webster. Encyclopedia Britannica, Inc.

⁴⁰ Vern L Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History (From Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation)*.

⁴¹ *Ibid*

Notably, although these nonprocreative activities are met with hostility, it appears that lesbianism is not as chastised as homosexuality.⁴² Throughout religious history, there was little to no mention of sexual intercourse between women. This has been attributed to the less importance attached to women, and therefore lesbianism.⁴³ From the foregoing, it is concluded that in both Judaism and Christianity, homosexuality is forbidden and heavily frowned upon.

2.2.1.3 Islamic Religion

In Islam, the proscription of homosexuality is rooted in the theologico-juridical *corpus* of Medieval Islam.⁴⁴ This *corpus* consists mainly of jurisprudence of the major Islamic Schools of Thought (*madhhab*) or *fiqh*, within Sunni Islam,⁴⁵ and is followed by most contemporary Islamic scholars.⁴⁶ Their views are based principally upon the *Qur'anic* parable of the Prophet Lot, or *Lūt* in Arabic.⁴⁷ In Islam, heterosexual marriages and their corresponding sexual relations are the only lawful and religiously recognised means of sexual contract.⁴⁸ Thus, it is right to observe that Islam takes no delight in the celebration of sexual diversity.

Interestingly, contrary to the common belief, the *Qur'an* does not expressly use terms corresponding to “homosexuals” or “homosexuality” within the entirety of its text⁴⁹ nor does the *Qur'an* prescribe death or any form of punishment for consensual homosexual or lesbian activity.⁵⁰ That is to say, there are no terms in the *Qur'an* which specifically denote same-sex relations, although there are certain terms that are frequently interpreted and are associated with same-sex practices.⁵¹ Nonetheless, in their traditional jurisprudence, unlawful sexual intercourse is referred to as *zina* which is a major offense.⁵²

⁴² Ibid

⁴³ Ibid 18

⁴⁴ Javaid Rehman and Eleni Polymenopoulou, *Is Green a Part of the Rainbow? Sharia, Homosexuality and LGBT Rights in the Muslim World* (2012).

⁴⁵ Mohammed Mezziane, 'Sodomie et Masculinité Chez les Juristes Musulmans du IXe au XIe Siècle' (2008) 55 *Arabica* 276, 278.

⁴⁶ Rehman and Polymenopoulou (n 42)

⁴⁷ Ibid

⁴⁸ Ibid

⁴⁹ Ibid

⁵⁰ Ibid

⁵¹ Ibid

⁵² Mohamed S El-Awa, *Punishment in Islamic Law: A Comparative Perspective* (2nd edn, 2000) 16–19; Noel J Coulson, 'Regulation of Sexual Behaviour under Traditional Islamic Law' in Afaf Lutfi al-Sayyid Marsot (ed), *Society and the Sexes in Medieval Islam* (1977) 63; Azman bin Mohd Noor, 'Stoning for Adultery in Christianity and Islam and Its Implementation in Contemporary Muslim Societies' (2010) 18 *Intellectual Discourse* 97; Nisrine Abiad, *Sharia, Muslim States and International Human Rights Treaty Obligations* (2008) 22–27

Also, the slight indifference of lesbian activity (*musahaqa*)⁵³, traces back to the disregard for women in many religious cultures as earlier mentioned, thus, the female homosexuality references to its punishment are scarce.⁵⁴ It is argued that female homosexuality is “treated with relative indulgence”: those who indulge in it incur only the same reprimand as those condemned for autoeroticism, bestiality, or necrophilia.⁵⁵ There remains an agreement between the four leading *Sunni* schools of thought and most Islamic scholars that homosexual acts are a major sin (*fahicha*) and may be punishable by death.⁵⁶

The *Shafi*, *Maliki*, and *Hanbali* schools generally prescribe the death penalty for penetrative same-sex intercourse, with general disagreements surrounding the mode of execution. Likewise, the *Jafari* School (*Shi'a*) also prescribes the death penalty. Only for the *Hanafi* School is homosexual conduct considered a slightly less serious offense and is punished through physical chastisement (at the discretion of the court); however, even for this School, the penalty of death may be awarded for a persistent offender. Likewise, for Islamic scholars who consider that the punishment of homosexuality is equivalent to the punishment for *zina*, the death sentence, provided the evidentiary requirements are met, may be also applied; married men who are offenders of *zina* (*muhsan*) face a mandatory death sentence, while flogging is applied to unmarried men (*ghayr muhsan*).⁵⁷

Juristic interpretation of homosexuality as an offense and sanctifying stoning by death (*rajm*) is derived from the narrative of the struggles of Prophet Lūt with his people. Lūt, or Lot, is referred to in the first book of the Bible, *Genesis*, and is described as the nephew of Abraham and guardian of the wealthy and ancient cities of Sodom and Gomorrah.⁵⁸ This story is similar to Christian doctrines as well. This is simply an indication that there is a coherent protest against homosexuality because it stems from spiritual teaching and is a gross violation to what these religious literatures seek to proclaim. It may even be observed that behaviour outside these teachings is an attack on their faith or reduction of the sacrosanctity and ultimate power of the doctrines. It could also be

⁵³ Sahar Amer, 'Medieval Arab Lesbians and Lesbian-Like Women' (2009) 18 *Journal of the History of Sexuality* 215–236.

⁵⁴ *Ibid*

⁵⁵ *Ibid*

⁵⁶ *Ibid*

⁵⁷ Rehman and Polymenopoulou (n 42)

⁵⁸ *Ibid*

observed that perhaps procreational values are secondary to the resentment of the homosexuality, but the passion and primary factor is the defacing of the command of the religious deities.

Although Islam acknowledges the vitality of sexual pleasure in marriage as consummation of marriage, thus, a condition of its legitimacy (*nikka*), it instructs that it must be performed within the bounds of Sharia.⁵⁹ Thus, any other act outside the heterosexual relations it mentions are proscribed.

As Fida Sanjakdar notes⁶⁰, “*deviating from the Islamic narrative of heterosexual relations within zawaj (marriage) is a highly charged and politically sensitive act, which can subject persons to ‘harsh criticism from fellow Muslims’ as well as becoming ‘ostracised from the Muslim community.’*”

2.2.1.4 *Hinduism*

Hinduism stands as one of the largest religions in the world, the third largest⁶¹ and oldest⁶², thus, essential for exploration.

In Hindu belief, there is a prolonged focus on the continuous process of birth and rebirth that ultimately releases the true self from the limitations of body and the ego a freeing of the spirit called *moksha*.⁶³ The process includes a release from sensual experiences including sexuality.⁶⁴

Notably, there is no distinction between homosexual and heterosexual experiences.⁶⁵ Hence, because, Hindu texts do not primarily discuss this, there is quite a disparity in attitudes concerning the *LGBTQ+* community in different temples and ashrams.⁶⁶ For further emphasis, the lack of moral doctrine on the topic makes it quite unclear to discern as right or wrong in the culture. Given this, it is fair to opine that Hinduism’s stance is nuanced. This is evidenced in the lack of consistency in Hindu text : while the *Arthashastra* argues that some homosexual intercourse is an

⁵⁹ Ibid

⁶⁰ Fida Sanjakdar, ‘Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning’ (2013) 13 *Sex Education* 16, 21.

⁶¹ Human Rights Campaign, ‘Stances of Faiths on LGBTQ+ Issues: Hinduism’ <https://www.hrc.org/resources/stances-of-faiths-on-lgbt-issues-hinduism>

⁶² ‘History Authors’, *History.com* <https://www.history.com/author/history>

⁶³ Human Rights Campaign, ‘Stances of Faiths on LGBTQ+ Issues: Hinduism’ <https://www.hrc.org/resources/stances-of-faiths-on-lgbt-issues-hinduism>

⁶⁴ Ibid

⁶⁵ Ibid

⁶⁶ Ibid

offence, the *Dharmashastra* condemns non-vaginal sex, requiring a purification ritual⁶⁷ whereas certain temples depict otherwise.⁶⁸ Additionally, it has been recorded that numerous Hindu texts have featured homosexual encounters depicting them as natural and joyful.⁶⁹

Furthermore, there are acceptances of narratives such as the third gender.⁷⁰ This category challenges gender and binary norms. In this, question rests on whether such is support of homosexuality as it includes effeminate males, masculine females, intersex people, adrogynes and transexual and transgender persons.⁷¹

2.2.2 Family Values and Societal Conformity

The concept of homosexuality has been met with scorn, and this paper reiterates such in various ways. Homosexuality has been called among other things a sin, an illness, a way of life, a normal variant of behaviour.⁷² Studies show that causes of homosexuality have been influenced by hormonal compositions, strong lack of parental presence, presence of dominating parent, inability to attract the opposite sex, rebellion against a bourgeois materialist society, or been victims of various kinds of traumatic experiences.⁷³ These homosexuals are seen as threats to family and traditional values by going public. They are met with backlash simply because they veer the expected terrain of social conformity.

It can be observed that society punishes non-conformist behaviours through various forms⁷⁴ including social exclusion, ridicule, discrimination, and violence.

“Sociologists have developed the concept of deviance to describe behaviour that violates social expectations or breaks social norms. In this sense homosexuality may be described as deviant behaviour, although in general we have avoided the use of the term in this paper because in our society deviance itself is stigmatizing. That is, to call someone a deviant is

⁶⁷ Qrius, ‘What Do Manusmriti and Dharmashastra Have to Say About Homosexuality?’ (19 July 2023) <https://qrius.com>.

⁶⁸ Raquel AG Reyes and William Gervase Clarence-Smith (eds), *Sexual Diversity in Asia, c.600–1950* (Routledge 2012) 50–51; SBS Language, ‘Same-Sex Marriage: Australia’s Hindu Clergy Group Supports “Yes” Campaign’ (2023).

⁶⁹ Nancy Bonvillain, *Women and Men: Cultural Constructs of Gender* (Prentice Hall 2001) 281 ; Sanskrit: तृतीय प्रकृति (*trtiya-prakṛti*), “third nature”

⁷¹ Ibid

⁷² Vern L Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History (From Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation)* 1.

⁷³ Ibid

⁷⁴ Matthew J Hornsey, Louise Majkut, Deborah J Terry and Blake M McKimmie, ‘On Being Loud and Proud: Non-Conformity and Counter-Conformity to Group Norms’.

the same as calling someone a bad name. One of the early theoreticians of deviance was Emile Durkheim, who observed that behaviour that qualifies one person for sainthood⁷⁵ may condemn another to prison, a mental asylum, or the stake. Durkheim urged sociologists to "abandon the still too widespread habit of judging an institution, a practice or moral standard as if it were good or bad in and by itself, for all social types indiscriminately."⁷⁶

The authors observe that homosexuality is likely to be treated with hostility in areas that uphold strong and seemingly unwavering moral and ethical values, for further description, societies that seem to be run by compasses of morality and corresponding values. For instance, modern African societies have expressed a strong distaste for the issue, and such revulsion has manifested in the anti-homosexuality laws such as the Anti-Homosexuality Act, 2023 of Uganda.

In Ghana, also, the Constitution of the Republic of Ghana 1992, from its very preamble amplifies certain core values, pillars and features upon which it is anchored.⁷⁷ These values are well intended to regulate the affairs of the people, their institutions and leaders.⁷⁸ In the comity of constitutional democracies, adherence and respect for the rule of law, the protection and preservation of fundamental human rights and freedoms of every individual, is invariably non-negotiable.⁷⁹ However, the operationalisation, enforcement and interpretation of any Constitution can stultify the realisation of these principles and portend an anathema to societal growth of nation state and the entire human race.⁸⁰

Hence, in Ghana, the social and cultural norms of homosexuality are pivotal to the acceptance or rejection as stated earlier.

⁷⁵ Tutor2U, 'Durkheim on Deviance' <https://www.tutor2u.net/sociology/reference/durkheim-on-deviance>.

⁷⁶ Vern L Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History (From Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation)* (New York: Garland 1979) 150.

⁷⁷ *Dr Prince Obiri-Korang v Attorney-General Writ No J1/18/2021* (Supreme Court of Ghana)

⁷⁸ *ibid*

⁷⁹ *ibid*

⁸⁰ *ibid*

Furthermore, as at 2015, Of the 76 countries that still criminalise same-sex relationships and behaviour, 38 are African. Recent surveys also show that the overwhelming majority of people who live in Africa strongly disapprove of homosexuality. This is even the case in South Africa, the only country on the continent that has legalised same-sex marriage.⁸¹

The authors wish to express that perhaps societies particularly Africa are strongly conformist in nature which means there is a grave expectation that every individual must align and match up to their attitudes, beliefs and behaviours and failure to which would attract ostracisation and neglect by the society.⁸² Homosexuality without doubt challenges the set of beliefs that Africans have on family life. ⁸³The unwillingness to compromise or submit to these values for change is what account for the hostility and movement against the course.

The authors further observe that persons who do not conform to the required standard set by a society or culture are likely to suffer societal punishment for their lack of conformity to the values and ethics provided. Thus, the practice of homosexuality stands as an act that falls short of the natural values and expectations on procreation, family life and sexual orientations held by conformist societies.

Values stand at the core to every going society. They are the ideals by which society progresses by. Values are meant to influence the growth of culture and are cherished due to its influence in determining behaviour necessary for social order and advancement. Thus, the evidence of non-conforming behaviour is perceived as a threat to social development and workforce productivity, a threat to procreation and ultimately the demise of a culture, group of people to which it seeks to prevent.

In Nazi Germany, homosexuals were put into concentration camps⁸⁴, while in Communist Cuba, they were tossed into political prisons, and when Castro's government finally opened the prisons, they were still denied the rights of ordinary citizens.⁸⁵ In the United States, they have been subject

⁸¹ The Conversation, 'Why Anti-Gay Sentiment Remains Strong in Much of Africa' (2015) <https://theconversation.com/why-anti-gay-sentiment-remains-strong-in-much-of-africa-42677>

⁸² Chris Drew, '22 Conformity Examples' (Helpful Professor, 2023) <https://helpfulprofessor.com/conformity-examples/>

⁸³ Academy of Science of South Africa, *Diversity in Human Sexuality: Implications for Policy in Africa* (2015)

⁸⁴ Concentration camps are facilities where governments detain large groups of people, often under harsh and inhumane conditions. They are typically used for political prisoners, minority groups, or perceived enemies of the state, often without fair trials. These camps have been associated with forced labor, starvation, torture, and mass killings.

Historically, some of the most infamous concentration camps were established by Nazi Germany during World War II, where millions, including Jews, Romani people, political dissidents, and others, were imprisoned and murdered in the Holocaust

⁸⁵ Vern L Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History (From Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation)* 2

to police harassment, entrapment, imprisonment, and exposure. Government repression has been encouraged by public pressure, since not only institutions such as churches but also individual family members have addressed the topic with hostility to the extent that homosexuals inevitably adopt a poor self-image.⁸⁶

Notably, although societies expect high conformity, it stands as an almost inevitable narrative that deviance is bound to happen despite the repression, oppression and discriminatory measures wired to compel persons to act according to their cultural values. Like the French sociologist Émile Durkheim opined, deviance is an inevitable part of how the society works and may much rather merit innovation and positive outcome.⁸⁷ However, question remains on whether such societies may be willing to embrace this position.

2.2.3 Science and Medicine

The debate on homosexuality from its inception has been an object of medical and scientific inquiry.⁸⁸ A possible reason for the controversy is the popular conception that homosexuality is biological defect.

To understand whether Homosexuality is an inherent trait in some humans, reference is first made to the work of Dr. Alfred Kinsey (1894-1956), an American biologist and a distinguished professor of entomology and zoology, who later became a trailblazer in the field of sexology. Initially focusing on the study of gall wasps, Kinsey's career took a significant turn when he began researching human sexuality, a topic that was highly controversial at the time.

Kinsey's research, particularly his extensive interviews and data collection, was ground-breaking and often met with both acclaim and criticism. By the end of 1940, he had documented over 450 homosexual histories, leading him to challenge prevailing psychological theories that labelled

⁸⁶ Ibid

⁸⁷ Emile Durkheim, *The Rules of Sociological Method* (1895)

⁸⁸ Jennifer Terry, *An American Obsession: Science, Medicine and Homosexuality in Modern Society*

homosexuality as an inherited abnormality. Kinsey argued that there was no scientific evidence to support the notion of homosexuality being inherent and unchangeable.⁸⁹

Long after the era of Alfred Kinsey, a handful of studies published during the 1990s have claimed to offer evidence in favour of a biological or genetic cause for homosexuality. Three of these in particular, a study of brain structure by Simon LeVay, a study of twins by J. Michael Bailey and Richard C. Pillard⁹⁰, and a study of “gene linkage” and “gene markers” by a team led by Dean H. Hamer⁹¹ attracted considerable media attention and are largely responsible for the popular belief that a “gay gene” has already been found.

There is not a single gene that determines whether a person is gay or lesbian. This is the primary takeaway from the most extensive genetic study on sexuality to date, published by Science.org⁹², a leading platform for scientific news, commentary, and innovative research. Science.org reaches an estimated global audience of over a million through its print and online editions. Its authors come from around the world, and its articles are among the most frequently cited in scientific literature⁹³.

The ground-breaking study, which included data from nearly half a million participants, effectively ends the debate about the existence of a "gay gene." Instead, the research concludes that human DNA cannot predict whether someone will be gay or heterosexual. Sexuality is influenced by life experience factors, as demonstrated by this study and others. The researchers found that sexuality is polygenic meaning hundreds or even thousands of genes make tiny contributions to the trait. That pattern is like other heritable (but complex) characteristics like height or a proclivity toward trying new things. (Things like red/green colour-blindness, freckles and dimples can be traced to single genes). Polygenic traits, however, can be strongly influenced by the environment, meaning there's no clear winner in this “nature versus nurture” debate

⁸⁹ Wardell B. Pomeroy, *Dr. Kinsey and the Institute for Sex Research* (New York: Harper & Row, 1972), 76.

⁹⁰ JM Bailey and RC Pillard, ‘Genetics of Human Sexual Orientation’ (1995) 6 *Annual Review of Sex Research* 126.

⁹¹ RC Pillard, ‘The Search for a Genetic Influence on Sexual Orientation’ in *Science and Homosexualities* (Routledge 2013) 226–41.

⁹² Science, ‘Association Study of Sexual Behaviour’ <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.aat7693>.

⁹³ Science, ‘Mission and Scope’ <https://www.science.org/content/page/mission-and-scope>.

Thus, the findings suggest that homosexuality or homosexual tendencies are not determined by biology or psychology indicating that sexual orientation is merely a matter of choice.⁹⁴

According to an article published by the Tech Interactive titled, “*is a person ‘born gay’, or is being gay a learned behaviour?*”⁹⁵ another possible explanation although merely a hypothesis is that, when examining large families, scientists observed that men with numerous older brothers were more likely to be gay.⁹⁶ This correlation persisted even when the siblings were raised separately, suggesting that the family environment was not a contributing factor. Therefore, it is likely that a biological mechanism is at play, however this has not been definitively established by current research

Although the exact cause remains uncertain, one hypothesis is that the presence of multiple male pregnancies alters the maternal womb environment. Subsequent male fetuses may develop brains predisposed to same-sex attraction.⁹⁷

One theory posits that a mother's body produces different chemicals and molecules when pregnant with a boy compared to a girl. With each male pregnancy, this "chemical memory" might become stronger, potentially affecting brain development in a way that influences sexual orientation⁹⁸. However, it is important to note that this hypothesis does not account for all cases; many men with older brothers are not homosexual, and many homosexual men do not have older brothers.

Nonetheless, the "fraternal birth order effect" provides compelling evidence of the interaction between genetics and the environment in determining sexual orientation⁹⁹. Scientists are only

⁹⁴ JM Bailey, PL Vasey, LM Diamond, SM Breedlove, E Vilain, MEpprecht, ‘Sexual Orientation, Controversy, and Science’ (2016) 17 Psychological Science in the Public Interest 45; D Scasta and P Bialer, American Psychiatric Association, ‘Position Statement on Issues Related to Homosexuality’ (2013) <www.psychiatry.org/psychiatrists/search-directories-databases/policy-finder>

⁹⁵ The Tech Interactive, ‘Ask a Geneticist: Homosexuality’ (2013) <https://www.thetech.org/ask-a-geneticist/articles/2013/homosexuality/>

⁹⁶ AF Bogaert, ‘Biological versus Nonbiological Older Brothers and Men’s Sexual Orientation’ (2006) 103 PNAS 10771.

⁹⁷ R Blanchard, ‘Fraternal Birth Order and the Maternal Immune Hypothesis of Male Homosexuality’ (2001) 40 Hormones and Behavior 105.

⁹⁸ T Casci, ‘Gay Genes Boost Fertility’ (2004) 5 Nature Reviews Genetics 884 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg1510>.

⁹⁹ Blanchard, R., 2001. Fraternal birth order and the maternal immune hypothesis of male homosexuality. Hormones and behavior, 40(2), pp.105-114.

beginning to understand the complex interplay between genetic and environmental factors in shaping human traits. It is likely that many other influences on sexual orientation remain to be discovered.¹⁰⁰

One highly publicised study that purported to demonstrate that sexual preferences and behaviour of homosexuals may be dictated by the structure of the brain was conducted in 1991 by former Salk Institute researcher Simon LeVay.¹⁰¹ LeVay studied the brains of cadavers, including 18 men known to have been homosexual and one known to have been bisexual. He compared them with the brains of another 16 men and six women whom he presumed to have been heterosexual. LeVay claimed that:

“INAH 3 was more than twice as large in the heterosexual men as in the women. It was also, however, more than twice as large in the heterosexual men as in the homosexual men. This finding indicates that INAH is dimorphic with sexual orientation [i.e., shows a difference in structure between homosexuals and heterosexuals], at least in men, and suggests that sexual orientation has a biological substrate.”¹⁰²

It must be noted that LeVay’s study, however, suffered from serious methodological errors, including the failure to adequately identify a control group. LeVay made questionable assumptions regarding the orientation of the “heterosexual” cadavers. He assumed that they were all heterosexual even though a number of the allegedly “heterosexual” subjects had died of AIDS, a disease that remains far more common among homosexual men than among heterosexuals: “Sixteen subjects were presumed to be heterosexual men: six of these subjects died of AIDS and ten of other causes.” In essence, Simon LeVay’s 1991 study on hypothalamic differences between homosexual and heterosexual men faced major methodological flaws that weakened its conclusions. Chief among them was the absence of a properly verified control group. LeVay assumed that all cadavers labelled “heterosexual” were indeed heterosexual, even though six of these men had died of AIDS a condition far more prevalent among homosexual men at the time.

¹⁰⁰ Ivanka Savic and Per Lindström, ‘Hormones and Human Sexual Orientation: Minireview’ (2008) *Endocrinology* (noting variance unexplained).

¹⁰¹ S LeVay, ‘A Difference in Hypothalamic Structure Between Heterosexual and Homosexual Men’ (1991) 253 *Science* 1034

¹⁰² *Ibid*

This assumption created a high risk of misclassification, undermining the reliability of his finding that homosexual men had a smaller third interstitial nucleus of the anterior hypothalamus (INAH-3).

Another anomaly of LeVay's study was that three of the "heterosexuals" had brain clusters smaller than the mean size for the homosexuals. On the other hand, three of the homosexuals had larger clusters than the mean size for "heterosexuals." Thus, LeVay was forced to admit, "The existence of 'exceptions' in the present sample (that is, presumed heterosexual men with small INAH 3 nuclei, and homosexual men with large ones) hints at the possibility that sexual orientation, although an important variable, may not be the sole determinant of INAH 3 size.

LeVay, in fact, admitted that his claim of a correlation between this brain structure and sexual orientation could not prove causation, or even the direction of influence, noting that "The results do not allow one to decide if the size of INAH 3 in an individual is the cause or consequence of that individual's sexual orientation, or if the size of INAH 3 and sexual orientation co-vary under the influence of some third, unidentified variable.

All 19 of his homosexual subjects had died of AIDS, and LeVay noted that another "problem" was "the possibility that AIDS patients constitute an unrepresentative subset of gay men, characterised, for example, by a tendency to engage in sexual relations with large numbers of different partners or by a strong preference for the receptive role in anal intercourse," both of which are major risk factors in acquiring Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection.

Again, another related issue was that the allegedly smaller brain clusters might not have caused homosexuality but instead could have resulted from sexual activity or AIDS-related brain damage. "*[T]here is the possibility that the small size of INAH 3 in the homosexual men is the result of AIDS or its complications and is not related to the men's sexual orientation.*" He further allowed that until "tissue from homosexual men dying of other causes becomes available, the possibility that the small size of INAH 3 in these men reflects a disease effect that is peculiar to homosexual AIDS patients cannot be rigorously excluded."

Due to discrepancies and methodological errors in LeVay's research, it was widely disregarded and rejected by other researchers. Byne and Bruce Parsons, in their article for Archives of General

Psychiatry, also questioned the potential impact of AIDS on LeVay's subjects.¹⁰³ They suggested a plausible mechanism whereby HIV infection might have selectively reduced the volume of INAH3 in homosexual men. Byne and Parsons further criticised LeVay's reliance on animal studies to support the idea that INAH3 is crucial for male-typical sexual behaviour.¹⁰⁴ Lastly, they pointed out several technical flaws in LeVay's study, including variable tissue fixation methods, inadequate sexual histories, and small sample sizes.¹⁰⁵

To date, no conclusive evidence has been found to assert that the brain structure of homosexuals differs significantly from that of heterosexuals. However, another study conducted by L. S. Allen and R. A. Gorski (1991) reported that the anterior commissure (AC) area of the brain was slightly larger in homosexual men compared to heterosexual men.¹⁰⁶ This finding was interpreted as supporting the hypothesis that sexual orientation may be linked to the sexually differentiated state of the brain.

Byne and Parsons noted that even if Allen and Gorski's findings were replicated, the size of the AC alone cannot determine an individual's sexual orientation. They highlighted that there was significant overlap in AC size between homosexual and heterosexual men; specifically, the AC size of 27 out of 30 homosexual men fell within the range found in 30 heterosexual men. Byne and Parsons also criticised Allen and Gorski's reliance on brains from subjects with acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) and the lack of detailed clinical history, suggesting that their study faces similar interpretive challenges as LeVay's study of the hypothalamus.¹⁰⁷

To date, humanity has not reached a conclusive consensus that homosexuality is an innate and universally inherent aspect of human nature. This ongoing lack of definitive proof has implications for its integration into global laws, particularly given its relatively recent recognition across many cultures. The argument follows that homosexuality is influenced by environmental factors rather than being universally inherent. Therefore, proponents suggest caution in imposing it as an

¹⁰³ W Byne and B Parsons, 'Human Sexual Orientation: The Biologic Theories Reappraised' (1993) 50 Archives of General Psychiatry 228, 235.

¹⁰⁴ *ibid*

¹⁰⁵ William Byne and Bruce Parsons, 'Human Sexual Orientation: The Biologic Theories Reappraised' (1993) 50 Archives of General Psychiatry 235

¹⁰⁶ LS Allen and RA Gorski, 'Sexual Dimorphism of the Anterior Commissure and Massa Intermedia of the Human Brain' (1991) 312 Journal of Comparative Neurology 97

¹⁰⁷ W Byne and B Parsons, 'Human Sexual Orientation: The Biologic Theories Reappraised' (1993) 50 Archives of General Psychiatry 228, 235

intrinsic facet of human existence on a global scale, emphasising the need for continued understanding and cultural sensitivity in navigating discussions and policies related to sexual orientation

Furthermore, many understand that there are various health implications or risks that may be associated with homosexuality particularly gayism. This appears to inform the substantial health disparity in homosexuals compared to heterosexuals so much that many protest movements and campaigns promoting homosexuality – a threat to health.¹⁰⁸

Studies reflect that there is heightened risk of chronic diseases such as cancers and mental health conditions associated with homosexuality.¹⁰⁹ Studies in North America prove that homosexuals report with poorer self-rated health and medical conditions such as HIV, asthma, diabetes, and high blood pressure.¹¹⁰ Considering this, it may be a fair concern as to why many frown upon on it as it is a perceived threat on public health and wellbeing.

¹⁰⁸ Paul Cameron, Kirk Cameron and Kay Proctor, 'Effect of Homosexuality upon Public Health and Social Order' (1989) 64 *Psychological Reports* 1167.

¹⁰⁹ Vanderbilt University Medical Centre (institutional source)

¹¹⁰ Richard Bränström and Mark Hatzenbuehler, 'Sexual Orientation Disparities in Physical Health' (2016).

CHAPTER THREE

HISTORICAL EVALUATION OF HOMOSEXUALITY

2.3 Introduction to the Evolution of Homosexuality

The essence of history as a guidepost to the present and possible future cannot be underestimated as it provides insight of the social metamorphism and foundation behind various practices.

As forementioned, the concept of homosexuality is not one of dying antique, thus, quite peculiar of every philosophical or social debate, there lies a long-standing history. This segment of the paper is dedicated to accounting for the history of homosexuality across the globe.

It has been registered that history does not make significant reference to homosexuality. Thus, it has been observed that the history of ancient homosexuality remains rather scanty if not difficult to retrieve. In the words of Bullough,

*To know about the sex life of anyone who lived in the past, it is necessary that they be famous in one way or another. History usually doesn't record the personal lives of obscure people. But in the case of homosexuality there are other difficulties. Few people publicly declared themselves as homosexual; in fact, the term was not even coined until the nineteenth century. Thus, the historian who wants to investigate homosexuals of the past has to follow all kinds of clues, weigh them, and then decide.*¹¹¹

From this extract, it may not be far-fetched to opine that history did not accord much respect to homosexuality, thus, persons of such nature strived to conceal any signs that may reveal so.

However, history raises some allegations. Sometimes it seems that almost everyone in the past has been claimed as homosexual, from Julius Caesar to John Edgar Hoover, often without the least foundation. In Caesar's case there is a bawdy song about an alleged affair with King Nicomedes

¹¹¹ Vern Bullough, *Homosexuality: A History from Ancient Greece to Gay Liberation* 139.

of Bithynia, a statement by a contemporary who allegedly called him the husband of all women and the wife of all men, and the reported homosexuality of some of those associated with him.¹¹²

However, these allegations are deemed as mere rumours as they are not supported by credible foundations.

2.4 Ancient Civilisations

It cannot be accurately held that attitudes towards homosexuality are of uniformity across cultures as such varied greatly within various civilisations. Nonetheless, sources suggest a general acceptance in ancient cultures such as Greece, Rome, Egypt, China, and Japan.¹¹³

2.4.1 Ancient Greece

In Ancient Greece yet another civilisation notable for its sophistication, same-sex relationships particularly between men were relatively recognised and accepted. However, such claim is not one of absolutism as a consensus of scholars seek to dispute this. Also, it is noteworthy that classical antiquity portrayed a diversity of distinct practices, each of which bore differing levels of acceptance depending on the time and place.¹¹⁴ Thus, although ancient Greece may have idealised homosexual relationship, this is not entirely correct.

Thomas K. Hubbard writes that:

The widespread notion that a “general acceptance” of homosexuality prevailed is an oversimplification of a complex mélange of viewpoints about a range of different practices, as is the dogma that a detailed regimen of protocols and conventions distinguished “acceptable” from “unacceptable” homosexual behaviours. There was, in fact, no more consensus about homosexuality in ancient Greece and Rome than there is today. In these heavily discourse-oriented cultures, as in our own, sexual dissidence was a flash point of ideological contention¹¹⁵

¹¹² Ibid

¹¹³ Robert M Baird and MK Baird (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Sexuality*

¹¹⁴ Thomas K Hubbard, ‘Introduction’ in *Homosexuality in Greece and Rome* (University of California Press 2003) xx–xxi.

¹¹⁵ Ibid

Hence, it can be noted that the idea of homosexuality was not entirely romanticised by ancient Greece as it is realised that while cities such as Sparta embraced it, cities like the Athens limited such practices.¹¹⁶

Homosexuality in Ancient Greece manifested in relationships known as pedagogical pederasty, which occurred between a man usually before the age of marriage and a freeborn boy.¹¹⁷This was instilled in their educational systems but moderated by strict social norms.¹¹⁸Pederasty was the practice where older men posed as mentors to younger men while maintaining sexual relations.¹¹⁹

Pederasty, as David Bain summarises in his review of by Harald Patzer, refers to “*the practice whereby young men pursue pubescent boys and enter into short-term relationships with them which expire when the boy becomes a man.*”¹²⁰

Pederasty in Ancient Greece was such that there was acknowledgement for romantic relationships between adult male (erastes) and younger males (eromenos)¹²¹

2.4.2 Ancient Rome

Pederasty was also practiced in Ancient Rome. Notably, although Ancient Greece and Rome are acclaimed for their advancement in various social, economic, scientific, and political endeavours, it is rather unfortunate that discussions between the differing cultures are lumped together as though they were of homogeneousness. Despite the similarities in culture, Ancient Rome tends to present a much-complicated perspective on pederasty where it reflected grave power dynamics and disparity in social statuses.¹²²In Ancient Rome, homosexuality manifested as slave-oriented and served as an avenue for slaves to improve their status. In this practice, freeborn men asserted dominance during these sexual encounters. One of the earliest literary pieces of evidence of Ancient Rome pederasty lies in Plautus’ comedy from around 200 B.C.E which takes a fairly benign view of pederastic liaisons as long as they involve slaves.¹²³

¹¹⁶ Big Think, ‘Pederasty and Homosexuality in Ancient Greece’ <https://bigthink.com/the-past/pederasty-homosexuality-ancient-greece/>

¹¹⁷Thomas K Hubbard, ‘Introduction’ in *Homosexuality in Greece and Rome* (University of California Press 2003)

¹¹⁸ Ibid

¹¹⁹ Ibid

¹²⁰ Ibid

¹²¹ CD Reeve, *Plato on Love: Lysis, Symposium, Phaedrus, Alcibiades with Selections from Republic and Laws* (Hackett 2006) xxi <https://books.google.com/books?id=E11QNf2EfeUC&pg=PP25>

¹²² Ibid

¹²³ Ibid

2.4.3 Ancient Egypt

Ancient Egypt sources are largely silent on the issue of same-sex attraction.¹²⁴ The insights of the topic are primarily speculations and mere myths such as the tale of Horus and Seth where Seth inebriates, seduces and inseminates Horus.¹²⁵ Again, the historical tale about Pharaoh Neferkare and his general Saseti is yet another account of homosexuality in Ancient Egypt.¹²⁶

Also, one of the most widespread indications is recognised in the depictions of tomb paintings of the two high officials Nyankh-Khnum and Khnum-hotep.¹²⁷ When these officials died, their families decided to bury them together in the same *mastaba*. Paintings in the mastaba showcase nose-to-nose touching which has been interpreted by many historians to mean kissing.¹²⁸ Nonetheless, many disagree to such interpretation, thus, this narrative is only understood as speculative.¹²⁹

2.4.4 Pre-Colonial Africa

Historically, writings on sexualities have been largely covered by non-Africans under an obscurity of political motivation.¹³⁰ Question remains whether earlier accounts on homosexuality are credible given that political writings at the time were fraught with biases and misconceptions about African culture and lifestyle. These European accounts paid no respect to the cultural diversity and independence of the various cultures in the continent.¹³¹

Each source is dated with varying degrees of precision adding further challenges to the historian's task of exploring and explaining change and continuity over time.

Notably, missionaries, colonial officials, and European travellers who expressed opinions about subtleties in African cultures in the name of science or civilisation often did so

¹²⁴ Neel Burtob, *The Oldest Gays in History* (2017)

¹²⁵ *Ibid*

¹²⁶ *Ibid*

¹²⁷ *Ibid*

¹²⁸ *Ibid*

¹²⁹ Richard Parkinson, 'Homosexual Desire and Middle Kingdom Literature' (1995) 81 *Journal of Egyptian Archaeology* 57.

¹³⁰ Oxford Bibliographies, 'Homosexuality in Ancient Egypt' <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/display/document/obo-9780199846733-0215.xml>.

¹³¹ David Schoenbrun, 'Early African Pasts: Sources, Interpretations, and Meanings' (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190277734.013.147>

*without the benefit of linguistic or cultural fluency, and to promote normative values or vested interests. This is a point that African and other critical scholars have frequently stressed in their own interventions, from Kenyatta's sarcastic comments on European "friends of Africa" in the 1930s (see Kenyatta 1961 under Anthropology), to richly theorised critiques such as Bibeau 1991, Arnfred 2004, and Tamale 2011*¹³²

This paper, however, accounts for homosexuality in pre-colonial Africa, a topic to which "anthropologists hid."¹³³ Same-sex relations has always existed in Africa, but this was much rather ignored or distorted rather than openly admitted.¹³⁴

As far back in the sixteenth century, Epprecht writes, "*Europeans did report sexual relationships between African men generally in horrified terms. For example, Andrew Battell, an English traveller, wrote that the Imbangala of Angola were "bestly in their living, for they have men in women's apparel, whom they keep among their wives.*"¹³⁵

Although many prefer to attribute homosexuality as a practice of western origin, it has been realised homosexuality also had some roots in pre-colonial Africa. What it meant to be a woman in many African pre-colonial societies was not rigid. "Among the Langi of northern Uganda," writes Sylvia Tamale, "*the mudoko dako, or effeminate males, were treated as women and could marry men.*" There were also the Chibados or Quimbanda of Angola, male diviners whom, some scholars have argued, were believed to carry female spirits through anal sex.¹³⁶

An anxiety that historians discern in this historical record is how uncomfortable European travellers, and later anthropological accounts were with the idea that their gendered worldview did not easily map onto the societies they encountered.¹³⁷

"*There is among the Angolan pagan much sodomy,*" wrote one Portuguese soldier in 1681 "*sharing one with the other their dirtiness and filth, dressing as women. And they call them by the name of the land, quimbandas.*"¹³⁸ This suggests that the idea of homosexuality cannot entirely pinned to

¹³² David Schoenbrun, 'Early African Pasts: Sources, Interpretations, and Meanings' (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190277734.013.147>

¹³³ JSTOR Daily, 'Anthropologists Hid African Same-Sex Relationships' <https://daily.jstor.org/anthropologists-hid-african-same-sex-relationships/>

¹³⁴ Ibid

¹³⁵ Ibid

¹³⁶ Mohammed Elnaiem, 'The "Deviant" African Genders That Colonialism Condemned' JSTOR Daily.

¹³⁷ <https://daily.jstor.org/anthropologists-hid-african-same-sex-relationships>

¹³⁸ Ibid

have originated from a particular culture although such practices may be more prevalent or accepted in one as against the other.

2.5 Medieval Period

The rise of various religious endeavours particularly Christianity greatly moulded societal attitudes towards homosexuality.¹³⁹ Biblical teachings condemning homosexuality in particular became motivation behind scorn and hostility associated with same-sex relationships. This paper has already highlighted the role of religion in driving the attitude and values concerned with the rejection of homosexuality, thus, there will be no further reiteration.

However, this section shall highlight the role of influential figures in early Christian literature such as St. Thomas Aquinas and St. Augustine who suggest that homosexuality is inconsistent with natural law, thus, short of the divine moral conscience bestowed on man during the medieval period.¹⁴⁰

St Augustine expressed his legendary antagonism towards same-sex relations. He stands as one of the earliest writers of the Church to claim that Sodom was destroyed for the sin of homosexuality.¹⁴¹ In his autobiographical masterpiece *Confessions*, Augustine chronicles the intensity of his struggles, providing a probing analysis of the human heart, the nature of sin, and the grace of the gospel. He appreciates that sex is a gift from God but does not serve us for the ultimate good.¹⁴²

In early Medieval Europe, there was no penance for homosexuality as it was treated like other sins.¹⁴³ However, in the 11th Century, *the Papal restoratio* informed harsher attitude, thus, ultimately leading to the criminalisation homosexual behaviour. In the 12th Century for instance, legal code

¹³⁹ Florence Tamagne, *A History of Homosexuality in Europe* (1919)

¹⁴⁰ Religious Tolerance, 'Homosexuality and the Bible' (archived 2020)
<https://web.archive.org/web/20200713060934/http://www.religioustolerance.org/hombibg193.htm>.

¹⁴¹ *ibid*

¹⁴² Chuck Colson, 'Finding Sexual Freedom in Augustine's Confessions' (2014) The Gospel Coalition
<https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/finding-sexual-freedom-in-augustines-confessions/>.

¹⁴³ Chuck Colson, 'Finding Sexual Freedom in Augustine's Confessions' (2014) The Gospel Coalition
<https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/finding-sexual-freedom-in-augustines-confessions/>.

of the Kingdom of Jerusalem, the Assizes of Jerusalem punished homosexual acts with castrations and subsequent medieval European laws furthered the severity of penalties.¹⁴⁴

Following the late 19th century to 1933, there was an activism led by Magnus Hirschfeld which marked the emergence of the first socio-political homosexual movement in Germany.¹⁴⁵ This movement focused on advocacy and acceptance of homosexual individuals. It made accomplishments such as the publishing of *Der Eigene* (The Unique), 1897, the world's first gay magazine.¹⁴⁶ This was geared to promote research on sexuality and homosexuality, heightening awareness on the topic amongst others¹⁴⁷

2.6 Early Modern Period

Even though there seemed to be improvements in Germany, the authors assert that this did not permanently erase the aggression addressed to the general treatment of the topic as the early modern period followed furthered persecution of homosexuality. However, such intensity of hostility varied across different religions and cultures. The Protestant Reformation and Catholic Counter-Reformation both reinforced negative views on homosexuality.¹⁴⁸ This period was characterised by its antagonistic laws towards same-sex relationships, notable amongst the laws was England's Buggery Act of 1533 which set sodomy as a capital offense.

Henry VIII was the first to criminalise homosexual activity in civil law in the form of the Buggery Act of 1533. Such behaviour had previously been regulated by ecclesiastical, or Christian, courts. The Act defined same-sex as 'the detestable and abominable vice of buggery', stating those found guilty should be sentenced to death.

¹⁴⁴ David C Nicolle, *The Crusader States and their Neighbours: A Military History, 1099–1187*.

¹⁴⁵ Magnus Hirschfeld, *The Homosexuality of Men and Women* (1914).

¹⁴⁶ JD Steakley, 'The Gay Movement in Germany, 1890–1933' (1975) 1 *Journal of Homosexuality* 147.

¹⁴⁷ Magnus Hirschfeld, *Berlins Drittes Geschlecht* (1903).

¹⁴⁸ Ted G Jellen, *Catholicism, Homosexuality and Same-Sex Marriage in the United States* (2009)

Members of the clergy, such as priests and monks, could also be executed under the Act, despite their immunity from being executed for murder.¹⁴⁹ This implies that murder was seen as a lesser crime than buggery to the extent that it broke the immunity enjoyed by the priests for offences such as murder. Alternatively, this may also suggest that Henry VIII was using civil law to limit the powers of the Catholic Church - the Act of Supremacy that declared him Supreme Head of the Church of England was passed only one year later. Whatever Henry VIII's motives, the Buggery Act was to remain in law in some form in England and Wales until 1967, indicating the long-lasting impact of his reign on the modern world.¹⁵⁰

Like the previous years, the 19th and 20th Centuries were met with more hostility, however, medicine started to play a vital role in the outlook of homosexuality. For further emphasis, the authors observe that there was significant shift from the religious overview of same-sex relationship as a sin to more of medical or psychological condition.

Even though the change in perspective, it remained widely punitive. In this, homosexuality was proscribed by law in many countries including the United Kingdom ¹⁵¹(evidence in the priorly mentioned Buggery Act 1533) and United States as evidenced in their sodomy laws. In the United States, this was realised where the Supreme Court upheld the constitutionality of Georgia sodomy laws in **Bowers v Hardwick**¹⁵², criminalising private oral and anal sex between consenting adults.

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The early 20th century was yet an exhibition of how psychology contributed to the general outlook of homosexuality. In the early 20th century, 1952, the American Psychiatric Association classified homosexual behaviour as a mental disorder listing it as “sociopathic personality disturbance.”¹⁵⁴ However, it has been recognised that this was not supported with any empirical or scientific evidence other than the natural sexual orientation.¹⁵⁵ Given this, it may be much rather substantial to conclude that there was no sufficient basis to identify homosexuality as a disorder rather than the realisation that it defrays from the expected standards of social conformity. Other sources such

¹⁴⁹ Buggery Act 1533

¹⁵⁰ Olivia Martin, Walter Hungerford and The Buggery Act: LGBTQ+ History and Punishment at The Tower of London (2021)

¹⁵¹ The case of Oscar Wilde's sentence to two years of hard labour for “gross indecency” under the Criminal Law Amendment Act 1885 in the United Kingdom proves so.

¹⁵² 478 U.S 186 (1986)

¹⁵³ However, this was later overturned by Lawrence v Texas 539 U. S 558 (2003) where it suggested that laws criminalizing sodomy between two consenting adults were unconstitutional.

¹⁵⁴ American Psychiatric Association, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (1952)

¹⁵⁵n re Marriage Cases 183 P 3d 384.

as the DSM-II (1968) also labelled it as sexual deviation ¹⁵⁶ while persons speculated that it was a contagious disease. However, in 1980, this was revised and noted as distress, that is, Ego-Dystonic Homosexuality. ¹⁵⁷ It was not until 1987 to 1990 that the indications of homosexuality were decoupled.¹⁵⁸

During the rise of World War II, there still remained a bitter resentment towards homosexuality. In Nazi Germany, the law reserved an antagonistic sentiment for the act in Paragraph 175 of the German Penal Code.¹⁵⁹ The effect of such paragraph made the act criminal – “unnatural vice” between men and indecent behaviour between men even without intercourse.¹⁶⁰ Also, the Law for Prevention of Hereditarily Diseased Offspring 1933 permitted the forced sterilisation of homosexuals.¹⁶¹ Given this, it would be rational to conclude that there was a gross violation of human rights of homosexuals that seemingly grew worse over the centuries.

The forced sterilisation was performed through vasectomy in the cases of men, salpingectomy for women and x-ray sterilisation in the case of both men and women.¹⁶² Such persons were considered “unfit” and “hereditarily diseased” yet again reflecting the contribution of science and medicine in forming the historical opinions of the subject. ¹⁶³ Over 400,000 persons fell victim to the oppressive law as nearly 200,000 to 400,000 persons suffered persecution.¹⁶⁴

Again, during World War II, gay men were persecuted and sent to concentration camps, where they were forced to wear pink triangles – a badge of shame.¹⁶⁵ This symbol permitted further dehumanisation and discrimination against them.¹⁶⁶

¹⁵⁶ American Psychiatric Association, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-II) (1968).

¹⁵⁷ American Psychiatric Association, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-III) (1980).

¹⁵⁸ American Psychiatric Association, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-III-R) (1987)

¹⁵⁹ German Penal Code (1935) §175

¹⁶⁰ Nazi Amendment to §175 (1935).

¹⁶¹ Law for the Prevention of Hereditarily Diseased Offspring (1933).

¹⁶² Stefan Kühl, Forced Sterilization and the Nazi Eugenics Program (2013).

¹⁶³ Reichsgesetzblatt (1933), I, 529

¹⁶⁴ Michael Burleigh, Death and Deliverance: Euthanasia in Germany 1900–1945 (Cambridge University Press 1994).

¹⁶⁵ Matt Mullen, ‘The Pink Triangle: From Nazi Label to Symbol of Gay Pride’ History.com <https://www.history.com/news/pink-triangle-nazi-concentration-camps>.

¹⁶⁶ Ibid

2.7 Post-World War and Gay Rights Movements

The *LGBTQ+* movement emerged in the late 20th Century.¹⁶⁷ The aftermath of the World War II increased the visibility and activism among homosexuals. In the United States, Post-World War II, there appears to be positive outcome in the movement of LGBTQ community to which includes homosexuals.

In the 1940s to 1950s, the gay rights movement gained momentum. *The Mattachine Society* (1950) and *the Daughters of Bilitis* (1955) were among the first gay rights organisations in the US.¹⁶⁸

Another pivotal turn was the Stonewall Riots which was triggered by a police raid on the Stonewall Inn.¹⁶⁹ Though the Stonewall uprising did not start the gay rights movement, it was a galvanising force for LGBT political activism, leading to numerous gay rights organisations, including the Gay Liberation Front, Human Rights Campaign, GLAAD (formerly Gay and Lesbian Alliance Against Defamation), and PFLAG (formerly Parents, Families and Friends of Lesbians and Gays). On the one-year anniversary of the riots on June 28, 1970, thousands of people marched in the streets of Manhattan from the Stonewall Inn to Central Park in what was then called “Christopher Street Liberation Day,” America’s first gay pride parade. The parade’s official chant was: “Say it loud, gay is proud.”¹⁷⁰ Afterwards, in 1970, there was the first gay pride parade in commemoration of the anniversary of Stonewall.¹⁷¹ Following this, there was a revision of the American Psychiatric Association Removes Homosexuality List of Mental Disorders in 1973 where there was a removal of homosexuality as a mental illness.¹⁷²

Afterwards, the advocacy for homosexuality has immensely increased given the rise of social media and the power of freedom of expression it affords to persons.

¹⁶⁷ Lillian Faderman, *The Gay Revolution: The Story of the Struggle*

¹⁶⁸ John D’Emilio, *Sexual Politics, Sexual Communities: The Making of a Homosexual Minority in the United States, 1940–1970* (1983)

¹⁶⁹ Martin Duberman, *Stonewall: The Definitive Story of the LGBTQ Rights Uprising That Changed America* (1993)

¹⁷⁰ History.com, ‘The Stonewall Riots’ <https://www.history.com/topics/gay-rights/the-stonewall-riots#stonewall-s-legacy>

¹⁷¹ David Carter, *Stonewall: The Riots That Sparked the Gay Revolution* (2010).

¹⁷² Ronald Bayer, *Homosexuality and American Psychiatry: The Politics of Diagnosis* (1981).

CHAPTER FOUR

THE RAPID CULTURAL SHIFT TOWARD ACCEPTANCE OF HOMOSEXUALITY FOLLOWING PROLONGED OPPOSITION

Introduction to the cultural shift towards the acceptance of homosexuality following prolonged opposition

To understand the growing acceptance of homosexuality and its associated aspects, it is essential to first consider the findings of the Pew Research Center on this topic. The Pew Research Center, a renowned organisation specialising in public opinion polling and demographic research, provides valuable insights into societal attitudes and trends¹⁷³. Their comprehensive studies reveal shifts in public perception, highlighting factors such as increased visibility of LGBTQ+ individuals, generational changes, and the impact of media representation. By analysing these findings, there is a gain of deeper understanding of the complex interplay between cultural, social, and political influences that contribute to the acceptance of homosexuality in contemporary society. Additionally, examining regional differences and the role of legal and policy advancements further enriches our comprehension of this evolving acceptance.¹⁷⁴

In the report issued by the Pew Research Center, it was asserted that, similar to findings from 2013 when the question was last posed, attitudes towards the acceptance of homosexuality are significantly influenced by the country in which individuals reside¹⁷⁵. People in Western Europe and the Americas generally exhibit higher levels of acceptance compared to those in Eastern Europe, Russia, Ukraine, the Middle East, and sub-Saharan Africa. Public opinion in the Asia-Pacific region tends to be divided on the issue. This variation is not only a reflection of the economic development of these nations but also their religious and political attitudes.

¹⁷³ Jens Krogstad, JS Passel and D'Vera Cohn, 'US Border Apprehensions of Families and Unaccompanied Children Jump Dramatically' (2016) Pew Research Center.

¹⁷⁴ Jess Lee and Catherine Bolzendahl, 'Acceptance and Rejection: Patterns of Opinion on Homosexuality in the United States and the World' (2019) 34(4) Sociological Forum.

¹⁷⁵ Pew Research Center, 'The Global Divide on Homosexuality' (2013) <https://www.pewresearch.org/global/2013/06/04/the-global-divide-on-homosexuality/>.

Despite these stark divides, there have been noticeable shifts in attitudes in many countries since Pew Research Center first began surveying this topic in 2002. For instance, in the United States, acceptance of homosexuality has risen from 49% in 2007 to 72% in recent years. In Kenya, public acceptance of homosexuality has risen notably, climbing from just about 1% in 2002 to approximately 14% in recent years. In contrast, data from the 2019 Afrobarometer survey indicate that attitudes in Ghana remain largely unfavorable, with more than 90% of respondents expressing intolerance toward homosexuals, leaving only about 7% who are accepting of homosexuality. This report highlights that age, education, income, and gender can significantly influence acceptance levels, with younger, more educated, and higher-income individuals typically showing greater acceptance.

Religion and its significance in people's lives also play a crucial role in shaping opinions on homosexuality. In many countries, individuals affiliated with religious groups are generally less accepting of homosexuality compared to those unaffiliated, often referred to as religious "nones." Political ideology is another important factor; individuals on the political right are generally less accepting than those on the left. In Europe, supporters of several right-wing populist parties are notably less likely to find homosexuality acceptable. This dynamic in Africa is just an outright rejection of homosexuality not based on political ideology but moral principles.

Furthermore, the report indicates that attitudes towards homosexuality strongly correlate with a country's economic status¹⁷⁶. In wealthier and more developed economies, such as Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany (with per-capita GDPs over \$50,000), acceptance of homosexuality is among the highest across the 34 countries surveyed¹⁷⁷. Conversely, in less wealthy countries like Nigeria, Kenya, and Ukraine (with per-capita GDPs under \$10,000), fewer than two-in-ten people believe that homosexuality should be accepted by society¹⁷⁸. This comprehensive analysis underscores the multifaceted nature of societal acceptance of homosexuality, influenced by a complex interplay of economic, religious, and political factors.

¹⁷⁶ *ibid*

¹⁷⁷ Saskia Keuzenkamp and David Bos, *Out in the Netherlands: Acceptance of Homosexuality in the Netherlands* (The Hague: Netherlands Institute for Social Research 2007)

¹⁷⁸ Anna Salnykova and Olena Hankivsky, 'Ukrainian Societal Attitudes towards the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Communities' in *Gender, Politics and Society in Ukraine* (University of Toronto Press 2012) 385–410

Religion, in terms of its relative importance in individuals' lives and specific religious affiliations, significantly influences perceptions of the acceptability of homosexuality across various societies globally. In 25 of the 34 countries surveyed, individuals who consider religion to be “somewhat,” “not too,” or “not at all” important in their lives are more likely to view homosexuality as acceptable compared to those who deem religion “very” important¹⁷⁹. For instance, in Israel, people who regard religion as less significant in their daily lives are almost three times more likely to believe that society should accept homosexuality than those who view religion as very important.¹⁸⁰

Religious affiliation also profoundly impacts attitudes towards the acceptance of homosexuality. Those who are religiously unaffiliated, often referred to as religious “nones” (including atheists, agnostics, or individuals identifying as “nothing in particular”), generally exhibit greater acceptance of homosexuality¹⁸¹. Although the opinions of religiously unaffiliated individuals can vary widely, in nearly every country surveyed with a sufficient number of unaffiliated respondents, these “nones” are more accepting of homosexuality than their religiously affiliated counterparts. Among the religiously affiliated, Christians are typically the comparison group. Within Christianity, Catholics are more likely to accept homosexuality than Protestants and evangelicals in many countries where there are enough adherents for analysis¹⁸².

In countries with significant Muslim populations included in the survey, acceptance of homosexuality is particularly low among adherents of Islam¹⁸³. For example, in Nigeria, acceptance of homosexuality is low among both Christians and Muslims, at 6% and 8%, respectively.¹⁸⁴ In Israel, Jews are much more likely to find homosexuality acceptable than Israeli Muslims, with acceptance rates at 53% and 17%, respectively. This analysis highlights the

¹⁷⁹ RJ Hamblin and AM Gross, ‘Religious Faith, Homosexuality, and Psychological Well-Being: A Theoretical and Empirical Review’ (2014) 18(1) *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Mental Health* 67

¹⁸⁰ Pew Research Center, ‘The Global Divide on Homosexuality Persists’ (25 June 2020) Washington DC https://www.pewresearch.org/global/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2020/06/PG_2020.06.25_Global-Views-Homosexuality_FINAL.pdf.

¹⁸¹ Amy Adamczyk and Carol Pitt, ‘Shaping Attitudes about Homosexuality: The Role of Religion and Cultural Context’ (2009) 38(2) *Social Science Research* 338.

¹⁸² L Poole, ‘The Catholic Homosexual’ (1975) 56(666) *New Blackfriars* 500

¹⁸³ *ibid*

¹⁸⁴ Pew Research Center, *The Global Divide on Homosexuality Persists* (25 June 2020, Washington DC).

complex interplay between religious beliefs and the acceptance of homosexuality, reflecting the diverse attitudes within and across different religious affiliations¹⁸⁵.

Research indicates that the increasing acceptance of homosexuality globally is primarily due to a decline in religious adherence among individuals. This phenomenon highlights a significant shift in societal values and attitudes towards homosexuality, particularly in regions where religious influence has traditionally been strong¹⁸⁶. Societies or countries with strong religious inclinations generally do not accommodate homosexuality and are largely opposed to its acceptance. Religious doctrines in these regions often explicitly prohibit homosexual behaviour, reinforcing conservative views and resistance to change¹⁸⁷.

Conversely, societies that are more accepting of homosexuality tend to have a weaker grasp on religious practices. These societies are more open-minded about homosexuality, often seeing no issue with it because they either lack religious affiliation, are not devout in their religious practices, or are indifferent to whether their religion frowns upon homosexuality. In such societies, secularism and liberal ideologies have gained prominence, leading to a more inclusive and accepting environment for diverse sexual orientations¹⁸⁸.

African countries, which are typically more religious than most Western nations, tend to be conservative on this issue, as their religious beliefs prohibit homosexuality. For instance, Ghana seeks to pass a legislation that criminalise homosexual acts, while Kenya has already implemented such laws, and countries like Uganda and Nigeria have similar prohibitions. These countries often justify their stance by citing religious texts and moral values deeply embedded in their cultural fabric. The influence of religious leaders and institutions plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion and policy on matters related to sexuality.

In contrast, many Western countries have experienced a significant decline in religious adherence¹⁸⁹. This trend is accompanied by a rise in secularism and the adoption of more

¹⁸⁵ *ibid*

¹⁸⁶ *ibid*

¹⁸⁷ *ibid*

¹⁸⁸ Pew Research Center, *The Global Divide on Homosexuality Persists* (25 June 2020, Washington DC).

¹⁸⁹ *ibid*

progressive values. As a result, these societies are more accepting of homosexuality, as there is no strong moral or religious framework opposing such behaviour. The lack of religious influence has led to a greater openness and acceptance of homosexuality in Western nations¹⁹⁰.

Additionally, the legal and political frameworks in Western countries have evolved to protect the rights of LGBTQ+ individuals. Laws supporting same-sex marriage, anti-discrimination policies, and public awareness campaigns have contributed to a more inclusive society. This legal recognition further reinforces the acceptance of homosexuality, providing a sense of legitimacy and protection to those who identify as LGBTQ+¹⁹¹.

Moreover, the media and popular culture in Western countries play a pivotal role in shaping public attitudes towards homosexuality¹⁹². Positive representation of *LGBTQ+* characters in films, television shows, and other forms of media normalise homosexuality and reduce stigma. Influential public figures and celebrities advocating for *LGBTQ+* rights also contribute to changing societal perceptions and fostering acceptance¹⁹³.

The generational shift in attitudes towards homosexuality is another significant factor. Younger generations, who are often less religious and more exposed to diverse cultures and ideas, tend to be more accepting of homosexuality. This generational change is gradually influencing older generations, leading to a broader acceptance of *LGBTQ+* individuals within families and communities.

Furthermore, international human rights organisations and advocacy groups such as Human Rights Watch (HRW) and International Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans and Intersex Association (ILGA World) have played a crucial role in promoting the acceptance of homosexuality worldwide. Through education, awareness campaigns, and lobbying efforts, these organisations work towards

¹⁹⁰ M Saez, 'The Global Struggle for LGBTQ Rights: Legal, Political, and Social Dimensions' (2016) 37(3–4) Women's Rights Law Reporter.

¹⁹¹ LM Roberts and RA Marx, 'The Persistence of Policies of Protection in LGBTQ Research & Advocacy' (2018) 15(4) Journal of LGBT Youth 280.

¹⁹² LB McInroy and SL Craig, 'Perspectives of LGBTQ Emerging Adults on the Depiction and Impact of LGBTQ Media Representation' (2017) 20(1) Journal of Youth Studies 32.

¹⁹³ TJ Billard and L Gross, 'LGBTQ Politics in Media and Culture' in Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics (2020).

dismantling discriminatory laws and practices. Their efforts have led to increased visibility and support for LGBTQ+ rights on a global scale.

In summary, the authors assert that the acceptance of homosexuality is closely linked to the level of religious adherence in a society. While religious societies tend to resist changes in attitudes towards homosexuality, secular and liberal societies are more open and accepting. The decline in religious influence, combined with legal recognition, media representation, generational shifts, and advocacy efforts, has contributed to the growing acceptance of homosexuality in many parts of the world. However, the path towards universal acceptance remains complex and multifaceted, requiring continued efforts to bridge cultural and religious divides and promote inclusivity and equality for all.

3.3 Legal Foundations and Theories: The Influence of the Devlin-Hart Debate on Contemporary Homosexuality Discourse

In 1957, a committee chaired by Lord Wolfenden recommended that consensual sexual activity between men in private should be decriminalised.¹⁹⁴ This recommendation rested in part on a view that the function of the criminal law was to preserve public order and decency, to protect the citizen from what is offensive or injurious, and to provide sufficient safeguards against exploitation and corruption of others and not to intervene in the private lives of citizens, or to seek to enforce any particular pattern of behaviour, further than is necessary to carry out the purposes outlined.¹⁹⁵

Hence, unless a deliberate attempt is made to equate the sphere of crime with that of sin, there must remain a realm of private morality and immorality which is not the law's business.¹⁹⁶ The committee's report provoked a famous reaction from Lord Patrick Devlin in his 1959 British Academy Maccabaeian lecture entitled "The Enforcement of Morals"¹⁹⁷. Although Devlin did not

¹⁹⁴ Matthew Grimley, 'Law, Morality and Secularisation: The Church of England and the Wolfenden Report, 1954–1967' (2009) 60(4) *Journal of Ecclesiastical History* 725.

¹⁹⁵ Wolfenden Committee, Report of the Departmental Committee on Homosexual Offences and Prostitution (Cmnd 247, 1957) 7

¹⁹⁶ *Ibid*, pg 9

¹⁹⁷ Patrick Devlin, 'Morals and the Criminal Law' (1965) 10 *The Enforcement of Morals*.

express it as straightforwardly as he might have, his basic point was that the criminal law is not (just) for the protection of individuals but also for the protection of society “the institutions and the community of ideas, political and moral, without which people cannot live together.” For that reason, he argued, the sphere of the criminal law should not, as a matter of principle, be limited to regulating conduct that has direct adverse effects on identifiable individuals.

Herbert Hart responded to Devlin, first in a radio broadcast subsequently published in *The Listener* magazine, and later in three lectures delivered at Stanford University in 1962 and subsequently published under the title *Law Liberty and Morality*. The positive aspect of Hart’s attack on Devlin was based on J. S. Mill’s so-called “harm principle¹⁹⁸”: *‘The only purpose for which power can rightfully be exercised over any member of a civilised community against his will is to prevent harm to others.’*

In 1965, Devlin published a revised version of the Maccabean lecture along with six other lectures on related topics under the title *The Enforcement of Morals*. The exchange between Hart and Devlin formed the basis of one of the most important jurisprudential debates of the second half of the 20th-century. Hart interpreted Devlin’s case for what has come to be called “legal moralism” (or “legal enforcement of morality”) as resting on two arguments, which he dubbed “the moderate thesis” and “the extreme thesis” respectively.¹⁹⁹ According to the former, a society is entitled to enforce its morality in order to prevent the society falling apart at the seams, as it were. According to the latter, a society is entitled to enforce its morality in order to preserve its distinctive communal values and way of life.²⁰⁰

Hart attacked the moderate thesis on the ground that it implied factual claims for which Devlin did not provide, and (in Hart’s view) could not have provided, substantial empirical support. For this reason, Hart read the moderate thesis as resting on a tautologous equation of a society with its morality and, therefore, true by definition: to attack a society’s morality is to attack society itself. Hart rejected the extreme thesis on the ground that it potentially justified legal enforcement of

¹⁹⁸ Nils Holtug, ‘The Harm Principle’ (2002) 5 *Ethical Theory and Moral Practice* 357.

¹⁹⁹ Russell Hittinger, ‘The Hart–Devlin Debate Revisited’ (1990) 35 *American Journal of Jurisprudence* 47

²⁰⁰ *ibid*

moral values, regardless of their content, simply because they were widely held.²⁰¹ He also thought that the thesis placed an unjustified brake on changes in social mores. Other important elements of Hart's case against legal moralism were distinctions between harm and offence, paternalism and moralism, positive and critical morality; and, within the criminal law, between principles of liability and principles of sentencing. These distinctions would be addressed in due course. Devlin had some contemporary supporters, but many subsequent commentators have accepted Hart's criticisms as effectively demolishing Devlin's position.

Since the initial exchange between Hart and Devlin, no theorist has devoted more attention to the general topic of the Debate than Joel Feinberg. His monumental four-volume work entitled *The Moral Limits of the Criminal Law* was published 20 years after the initial exchange²⁰². Feinberg contributed to the Debate in three important ways. First, he analysed in detail the concepts of harm, offence, paternalism, and moralism, and developed principles that would enable these concepts to be applied in practice. Secondly, he distinguished between harmfulness and wrongfulness. The criminal law is justified in prohibiting harmful conduct (Feinberg argues) only if that conduct is also wrong.²⁰³ Harm may be a necessary condition, but it is not a sufficient condition, of criminalisation. Feinberg defines harm in terms of a setback to a person's interests and wrongfulness in terms of invasion of a right that such an interest be protected. Feinberg's third contribution is a perhaps-unintended corollary of the first two.²⁰⁴

Like many "liberal" contributors to the debate, Feinberg begins with a "presumption in favor of individual liberty." This means (in his terms) that everyone has both an interest in freedom of action and a (presumptive) right that that interest be protected²⁰⁵. It follows that restricting a person's freedom of action causes them harm. In these terms, what the harm principle says is that the harm of restricting a person's protected interest in freedom of action can be justified only if the person has caused wrongful harm to another or has, in other words, wrongfully invaded an

²⁰¹ HLA Hart, *Law, Liberty and Morality* (OUP 1963) 49–50

²⁰² Joel Feinberg, *The Moral Limits of the Criminal Law, Volume 1: Harm to Others* (OUP 1987)

²⁰³ *ibid*

²⁰⁴ *ibid*

²⁰⁵ *ibid*

interest of the other. Since there is harm on both sides of the equation, as it were, determining the limits of the criminal law depends on weighing one harm against the other or, in other words, balancing conflicting interests.

A lawmaker faced with a decision whether or not to criminalise particular conduct must decide whether or not the interest in being free to engage in that conduct outweighs the interest in not being adversely affected by it. Feinberg reaches much the same conclusion as a result of developing what he calls “mediating principles,” which he considers to be necessary in order to make the abstract harm principle practically useful.²⁰⁶

The relative “importance” of the interest harmed by particular conduct and the interest in engaging in that conduct, Feinberg argues, is relevant to determining in practice whether the criminal law is justified in regulating the conduct. Both lines of argument suggest that determining the limits of the criminal law is better understood in terms of reconciling the competing interests of agents and those adversely affected by their conduct, than in terms of implementing a presumption in favor of the agent’s freedom of action.

Feinberg’s third contribution to the Debate, then, was to demonstrate (perhaps unwittingly) that the process of giving practical effect to the harm principle may lead us to re-evaluate the “lexical” priority of freedom of action which is assumed to underpin it. One important consequence of making explicit the distinction between wrongfulness and harmfulness was reconceptualisation of the debate in terms of whether it is ever justifiable to criminalise conduct merely on the ground that it is wrongful, regardless of whether it is (and even if it is not) harmful.

Whereas Feinberg proposed wrongfulness as an additional, necessary condition for criminalisation, others have considered whether it might operate as an alternative, sufficient condition. For instance, John Gardner and Stephen Shute have argued that rape is prohibited because it involves wrongful invasion of a person’s sexual autonomy²⁰⁷. Nevertheless it is argued that, criminalisation of rape does not offend the harm principle because that principle does not require that harm be caused to identifiable individuals because of instances of criminal conduct,

²⁰⁶ *ibid*

²⁰⁷ John Gardner and Stephen Shute, ‘The Wrongness of Rape’ in *Oxford Essays in Jurisprudence* vol 4 (2000)

but only that society would be harmed if rape were not a criminal offence. On the assumption that if rape were not a criminal offence, it would occur more often, the result would be a society where people felt more insecure and enjoyed less sexual autonomy. In short (say Gardner and Shute)²⁰⁸, raping a person is wrong even if it causes the person no harm, and a society in which rape was not criminalised would be a worse society to live in than those where it is.

The central question raised by the Hart–Devlin Debate, whether the law should enforce society’s moral convictions even in the absence of demonstrable harm, remains profoundly relevant to the issue of homosexuality. Lord Devlin’s position, grounded in legal moralism, suggested that society is entitled to criminalise acts that are deemed morally unacceptable by the community, even when performed privately, because shared morality constitutes the fabric of social cohesion.²⁰⁹ On this logic, same-sex relations could be seen as undermining collective moral values and thus threatening social stability.

In contrast, H. L. A. Hart’s liberal argument, grounded in John Stuart Mill’s harm principle, rejects that reasoning. Hart maintained that the criminal law should only intervene to prevent harm to others, not to impose the moral views of the majority on private behavior. When applied to homosexuality, Hart’s framework would render the criminalisation of consensual same-sex conduct unjustifiable, since such acts, when conducted privately between consenting adults, do not cause direct harm to others or infringe upon their rights. Thus, in Hart’s view, morality alone is not a sufficient basis for criminal sanctions.

Building upon Hart’s position, Joel Feinberg’s refinement of the harm principle reinforces this conclusion. Feinberg distinguishes between harm (a wrongful setback to one’s interests) and wrongfulness (a violation of a protected right). By his reasoning, criminal law is warranted only when an individual’s conduct is both harmful and wrongful toward another.²¹⁰ Homosexual acts between consenting adults do not meet these conditions. They neither violate another’s rights nor cause wrongful harm. On the contrary, criminalising such conduct inflicts harm by restricting

²⁰⁸ *ibid*

²⁰⁹ Patrick Devlin, *The Enforcement of Morals* (OUP 1965) 10–13

²¹⁰ Joel Feinberg, *Harm to Others* (OUP 1984) 31–34

individual liberty, autonomy, and dignity, values which, according to Feinberg, enjoy presumptive protection under liberal principles of justice.

Furthermore, Feinberg's concept of balancing harms, weighing the harm of restricting freedom against any harm caused by the conduct, also tilts in favour of decriminalisation. The harm of punishing individuals for consensual intimacy far exceeds any speculative "social harm" arising from moral disapproval. Indeed, contemporary evidence suggests that criminalisation itself generates tangible harms such as stigmatisation, discrimination, and psychological distress, while the conduct it seeks to suppress causes none to others.

Gardner and Shute's argument that certain acts, such as rape, may be criminalised because they are inherently wrongful even if they cause no immediate harm, cannot be analogously applied to homosexuality.²¹¹ Rape is intrinsically wrongful because it violates another's sexual autonomy and consent, which are core rights protected by both moral and legal systems.²¹² Homosexual conduct, by contrast, involves mutual consent and shared sexual autonomy; there is no comparable violation. Therefore, applying Gardner and Shute's framework, it would be incoherent to classify consensual homosexual behavior as wrongful, since its defining feature is respect for mutual autonomy, not its denial.

Thus, under the logic developed from Hart through Feinberg to Gardner and Shute, the criminalisation of homosexuality cannot be justified either on grounds of harm, wrongfulness, or societal preservation. To the contrary, decriminalisation affirms the liberal presumption in favour of personal liberty and autonomy, which are themselves moral goods central to a free society. Devlin's claim that shared morality is necessary for social cohesion might once have reflected the prevailing sentiment of his era, but as moral pluralism and human rights norms have expanded, Hart's position has proven more ubiquitous in the global legal order. The law, as Hart foresaw, must protect individuals from coercion by the moral majority, not act as its enforcer.

²¹¹ John Gardner and Stephen Shute, 'The Wrongness of Rape' (2000) 20 *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies* 575, 579–84.

²¹² *ibid*

In the contemporary human rights context, this reasoning aligns with international standards such as those articulated by the UN Human Rights Committee and regional human rights courts, which interpret privacy, equality, and dignity as fundamental values outweighing mere moral disapproval, although this mostly holds true in the west. The progression from Devlin's moralism to Hart's liberalism, refined by Feinberg's analytical clarity, provides a jurisprudential foundation for the ongoing global shift toward possible recognition and protection of homosexual rights.

Current Philosophy on The Matter and Position of The Law on The Matter

It remains the assertion of the authors that, the rights of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender (*LGBT*) individuals exhibit a vast range of variability across different countries and jurisdictions, reflecting diverse cultural, religious, and legal landscapes. These rights span from the legal recognition of same-sex marriage to the imposition of the death penalty for homosexual acts. As of May 2024, 37 countries had accepted homosexuality,²¹³ showcasing significant progress in the recognition and acceptance of *LGBT* rights in these regions. This milestone marks a substantial shift in societal attitudes towards same-sex relationships, providing legal and social recognition to couples and affording them rights and protections previously denied.

In stark contrast, the legal landscape in other parts of the world remains punitive towards *LGBT* individuals. Apart from actions by non-state actors and extrajudicial killings, only two countries Iran and Afghanistan, 21 are believed to actively impose the death penalty for consensual same-sex sexual acts²¹⁴. These nations enforce stringent measures against homosexual activities, reflecting deep-seated cultural and religious prohibitions. Additionally, countries such as Mauritania, Saudi Arabia, Somalia (specifically in the autonomous state of Jubaland), and the United Arab Emirates maintain the death penalty in their legal codes, although it is generally not

²¹³ Pew Research Center, 'Same-Sex Marriage Around the World' (9 June 2023)

²¹⁴ Kameel Ahmady et al, *Forbidden Tale: A Comprehensive Study on Lesbian, Gay, Bisexuals (LGB) in Iran* (Lambert Academic Publishing 2020).

enforced. This existence of such severe penalties, even if not commonly applied, underscores the perilous legal environment for *LGBT* individuals in these regions.

Moreover, *LGBT* individuals in the Russian region of Chechnya face extrajudicial killings amongst others, highlighting the extreme dangers and systemic persecution endured.²¹⁵ In a somewhat positive development, Sudan rescinded its unenforced death penalty for anal sex, whether heterosexual or homosexual.

However, fifteen countries still have stoning as a legal penalty for adultery, which, due to the illegality of same-sex marriage in these jurisdictions, encompasses homosexual acts by default. This punitive measure is actively enforced by legal authorities in Iran and the northern regions of Nigeria, exemplifying the extreme and brutal measures still prevalent in certain parts of the world.²¹⁶

In the landmark move in 2011, the United Nations Human Rights Council passed its first resolution recognising *LGBT* rights. This resolution was a significant step towards international recognition and protection of *LGBT* individuals' rights.²¹⁷ Following the resolution, the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights issued a comprehensive report documenting widespread violations of *LGBT* rights, including hate crimes, criminalisation of homosexual activity, and systemic discrimination. The report underscored the urgent need for protective legislation and called on all countries to enact laws safeguarding basic *LGBT* rights.

A study conducted in 2022 revealed a correlation between *LGBT* rights, as measured by ILGA-Europe's Rainbow Index, and a reduced incidence of HIV/AIDS among gay and bisexual men, independent of risky sexual behaviour.²¹⁸ This finding underscores the broader public health implications of recognising and protecting *LGBT* rights, suggesting that inclusive and supportive legal environments contribute to better health outcomes for marginalised communities.²¹⁹

²¹⁵ IME.com, 'He Was Targeted in Chechnya for Being Gay. Now, He's Being Hunted in Europe'.

²¹⁶ Ardo Hazzad, 'Nigerian Islamic Court Orders Death by Stoning for Men Convicted of Homosexuality' (2 July 2022).

²¹⁷ Jill Dougherty, 'UN Council Passes Gay Rights Resolution' (CNN, 17 June 2011) archived 30 September 2018.

²¹⁸ Kristefer Stojanovski, Elizabeth J King, K Rivet Amico, Marisa C Eisenberg, Arline T Geronimus, Sladjana Baros, Axel J Schmidt, 'Stigmatizing Policies Interact with Mental Health and Sexual Behaviours to Structurally Induce HIV Diagnoses Among European Men Who Have Sex with Men' (2022) 26(10) *AIDS and Behavior* 3400.

²¹⁹ *ibid*

Despite these advancements and the growing acceptance of *LGBT* rights in many Western countries, global attitudes towards homosexuality remain deeply divided. Particularly in the eastern and southern parts of the world, resistance to *LGBT* rights persists, fueled by entrenched cultural, religious, and societal beliefs.²²⁰ These regions often view homosexual tendencies as unnatural and not inherent to human nature, leading to widespread social rejection and legal discrimination against *LGBT* individuals.

The authors contend that the global hesitance to fully embrace *LGBT* rights stems from the belief that homosexual tendencies are not an inherent aspect of humanity and thus do not warrant recognition as fundamental human rights. This perspective leads many countries to adopt a positivist approach to legislating on *LGBT* issues, treating these rights as contingent upon societal norms and legislative discretion rather than as inalienable rights. As a result, the legal frameworks in these regions mirror broader societal attitudes and cultural values, often resulting in restrictive and punitive measures against *LGBT* individuals.

This perception of homosexuality as unnatural and morally unacceptable persists in many parts of the world. For instance, out of the 195 recognised countries globally²²¹, only around 40 countries recognise same-sex relationships or provide some level of legal protection to *LGBT* individuals. This stark divide underscores the prevailing philosophy in many regions that homosexuality is an abomination, unworthy of legal recognition or protection.

The adoption of a positivist approach means that the inclusion of *LGBT* rights in legislation is highly dependent on the prevailing cultural, religious, and societal attitudes within each jurisdiction. Countries that oppose *LGBT* rights often do so based on deeply ingrained beliefs and values. For example, in many African and Middle Eastern countries, homosexuality is not only socially stigmatised but also criminalised, with severe penalties including imprisonment and, in some cases, the death penalty. Nigeria, for example, has laws in the northern regions that impose the death penalty for homosexual acts, reflecting the strong influence of conservative religious doctrines on the legal system.²²²

²²⁰ Amy Adamczyk, Chunrye Kim and Margaret Schmuhl, 'Newspaper Presentations of Homosexuality across Nations: Examining Differences by Religion, Economic Development, and Democracy' (2018) 61(3) *Sociological Perspectives* 399 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26580578>

²²¹ Science Focus, 'How Many Countries Are There' <https://www.sciencefocus.com/planet-earth/how-many-countries-are-there>

²²² International Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans and Intersex Association (ILGA World), *State-Sponsored Homophobia: Global Legislation Overview – December 2020* (Geneva 2020).

In contrast, countries that recognise *LGBT* rights often have more progressive social attitudes and a stronger emphasis on human rights. For instance, Canada and several European nations, such as the Netherlands and Sweden, have comprehensive legal protections for *LGBT* individuals, including the recognition of same-sex marriage and anti-discrimination laws. These countries treat *LGBT* rights as inherent human rights, integral to their legal and social frameworks²²³.

The divided position on *LGBT* rights across jurisdictions indicates that there is no definitive global stance on the issue. The concept of *LGBT* rights remains in a constant state of flux, influenced by ongoing social, cultural, and political changes. International advocacy and human rights organisations continue to push for broader recognition and protection of *LGBT* rights, but progress is uneven and often met with resistance.²²⁴ To achieve a more unified and inclusive approach to *LGBT* rights, it is crucial to address the underlying cultural and societal beliefs that contribute to resistance. Education, dialogue, and advocacy are essential tools in changing perceptions and promoting the understanding that since *LGBT* rights are not fundamental human rights, people who happen to be members of such communities should not be discriminated against or abused in any form or manner whatsoever. By highlighting the positive impacts of inclusive policies and fostering respect for diversity, there can be a gradual shift towards heterosexuals and homosexuals living in a harmonised environment without any dispute.

A Contemporary Examination of Homosexuality in the African Context

As previously discussed, homosexuality in many African countries has been met with significant disdain and hostility. For nearly two decades, African leaders have openly criticised the acceptance of homosexuality within their borders²²⁵, reinforcing traditional and conservative views.

²²³ John McAllister, 'Tswanarising Global Gayness: The "UnAfrican" Argument, Western Gay Media Imagery, Local Responses and Gay Culture in Botswana' (2013) 15 *Culture, Health & Sexuality* S88 <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23524931>.

²²⁴ Jess Lee and Catherine Bolzendahl, Review of Acceptance and Rejection: Patterns of Opinion on Homosexuality in the United States and the World by Peter Hart-Brinson and Amy Adamczyk (2019) 34(4) *Sociological Forum* 1024 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48558587>.

²²⁵ DW.com, 'Why Do LGBTQ Rights Face So Much Opposition in Africa' <https://www.dw.com/en/why-do-lgbtq-rights-face-so-much-opposition-in-africa/a-65441709>.

In recent years, this opposition has manifested in the enactment of stringent legislation aimed at combating homosexuality and its associated tendencies.²²⁶ The topic of homosexuality has been a contentious issue in African societies, often rooted in deep-seated cultural, religious, and historical contexts. Many African leaders have framed homosexuality as a Western imposition that threatens traditional values and social norms.²²⁷

A good exemplification of this is when former Zimbabwean President Robert Mugabe notoriously described homosexuals as "worse than dogs and pigs" and vehemently opposed any attempts to legalise same-sex relationships²²⁸.

The authors maintain that the disdain for homosexuality in Africa is often justified by cultural and religious beliefs. Many African societies hold traditional views of gender and sexuality, which are reinforced by religious teachings.²²⁹ Both Christianity and Islam, the dominant religions on the continent, generally espouse conservative views on sexuality.²³⁰ Religious leaders often play a significant role in shaping public opinion and influencing legislative actions²³¹. In Uganda, evangelical Christian groups have been instrumental in advocating for stringent anti-LGBTQ laws, framing the issue as a moral and spiritual battle. There were efforts in Uganda to institute the death penalty for homosexuality until March 22, 2023, where gay sex is punishable by the death penalty or life imprisonment²³²

In a 2014 interview with CNN, Museveni described homosexuals as "disgusting", saying that their acts are "unnatural" and that he would be able to ignore them if it was proven that "[he] is born that way". He also said that he had appointed a group of scientists in Uganda to determine if homosexuality was a learned orientation²³³. This led to widespread criticism from the scientific community, with an academic of the National Institutes of Health calling on his Ugandan

²²⁶ Patrick Awondo, Peter Geschiere and Graeme Reid, 'Homophobic Africa? Toward a More Nuanced View' (2012) 55(3) *African Studies Review* 145

²²⁷ GhanaWeb, <https://www.ghanaweb.com/GhanaHomePage>.

²²⁸ Reuters, 'Worse than Dogs and Pigs: Life as a Gay Man in Zimbabwe' (Reuters, 1 September 2017)

<https://www.reuters.com/article/world/worse-than-dogs-and-pigs-life-as-a-gay-man-in-zimbabwe-idUSKCN1BF03Z/> accessed 18 December 2025.

²²⁹ Kwame Essien and Saheed Aderinto, 'Cutting the Head of the Roaring Monster: Homosexuality and Repression in Africa' (2009) 30(3) *African Study Monographs* 121.

²³⁰ *Supra*

²³¹ CNN, 'Museveni Assents Homosexuality Bill' (29 May 2023) <https://edition.cnn.com/2023/05/29/africa/museveni-assents-homosexuality-bill-intl/index.html>.

²³² Steven Chase, 'Harper Lobbies Uganda on Anti-Gay Bill' *The Globe and Mail* (29 November 2009).

²³³ <https://edition.cnn.com/2014/02/24/world/africa/uganda-homosexuality-interview/index.html>

counterparts to reconsider their findings.²³⁴ As of March 22, 2023, Uganda passed the Anti-Homosexuality Act, 2023 illegalise the act of identifying as LGBT, making it punishable by life imprisonment, and imposing the death penalty for aggravated gay sex²³⁵. Similarly, Islamic leaders in Nigeria have supported harsh penalties for homosexuality, citing religious texts that condemn same-sex relations²³⁶.

The legislative landscape in Africa regarding homosexuality and LGBTQ rights is characterised by a strong resistance rooted in cultural, religious, and historical contexts. While some progress has been made in certain areas, the overall trend remains one of opposition and criminalisation.

To address these issues effectively, there must be a nuanced understanding of the socio-cultural dynamics at play, alongside continued advocacy and dialogue aimed at fostering greater acceptance and protection for LGBTQ individuals across the continent.

In recent years, numerous African countries have taken legislative measures to curb homosexuality. These laws vary in severity but generally reflect a widespread intolerance towards LGBTQ individuals.

In 2014, Nigeria passed the Same-Sex Marriage (Prohibition) Act²³⁷, which not only bans same-sex marriage but also criminalises the registration of gay clubs, societies, and organisations, and imposes a 14-year prison sentence for anyone entering into a same-sex marriage or civil union. Additionally, public displays of affection between same-sex couples are met with harsh penalties²³⁸.

Uganda followed suit when it first introduced same in 2009, garnered international attention for its severe punishments, including life imprisonment for certain homosexual acts. Although the law was annulled in 2014 on procedural grounds, the Ugandan government has continued to push for

²³⁴ Elizabeth Landau, Zain Verjee and Antonia Mortensen, 'Uganda President: Homosexuals Are "Disgusting"' CNN (25 February 2014).

²³⁵ Larry Madowo and Catherine Nicholls, 'Uganda Parliament Passes Bill Criminalizing Identifying as LGBTQ, Imposes Death Penalty for Some Offenses' CNN (21 March 2023).

²³⁶ Human Rights Watch, 'Nigeria: Anti-LGBT Law Threatens Basic Rights' (14 January 2014) <https://www.hrw.org/news/2014/01/14/nigeria-anti-lgbt-law-threatens-basic-rights>.

²³⁷ Nigeria, Same Sex Marriage (Prohibition) Act 2013 (17 December 2013) <https://www.refworld.org/legal/legislation/natlegbod/2013/en/19556> accessed 5 March 2025.

²³⁸ Nigerian Criminal Code, ch 21 (archived 20 July 2017, retrieved 1 March 2012).

similar legislation.²³⁹ In 2023, Uganda's Parliament passed a new Anti-Homosexuality Bill, reinforcing the country's hardline stance against LGBTQ individuals.

Another example is Kenya who have enacted similar legislation seeking to proscribe homosexuality.²⁴⁰ These laws prescribe up to 14 years in prison for individuals found guilty of homosexual acts. Kenyan leaders, including President Uhuru Kenyatta, have publicly stated that homosexuality is inconsistent with Kenyan culture and values.

The legislative trend across Africa reflects broader societal attitudes that view homosexuality as incompatible with cultural and religious norms. For instance, in The Gambia, former President Yahya Jammeh led the call for legislation that would set laws against homosexuals that would be "stricter than those in Iran", and that he would "cut off the head" of any gay or lesbian person discovered in the country.²⁴¹ Furthermore, news reports indicated his government intended to execute all homosexuals in the country.

In a speech to the United Nations on 27 September 2013, Jammeh said that "homosexuality in all its forms and manifestations which, though very evil, antihuman as well as anti-Allah, is being promoted as a human right by some powers", and that those who do so "want to put an end to human existence."²⁴² In 2014, Jammeh called homosexuals "vermin" by saying that "We will fight these vermin called homosexuals or gays the same way we are fighting malaria-causing mosquitoes, if not more aggressively". He also went on to disparage LGBT people by saying that "As far as I am concerned, LGBT can only stand for Leprosy, Gonorrhoea, Bacteria and Tuberculosis; all of which are detrimental to human existence"

This perspective is not limited to a few nations but is widespread across the continent. For instance, countries like Tanzania and Ghana have also seen increased legislative and societal pressures against *LGBTQ* communities.

The former president of Zimbabwe, Robert Mugabe, was uncompromising in his opposition to LGBT rights in Zimbabwe. In September 1995, Zimbabwe's parliament introduced legislation

²³⁹ Uganda, Anti-Homosexuality Act 2014 (legislative history: Anti-Homosexuality Bill 2009, introduced 14 October 2009).

²⁴⁰ Kenya, Penal Code ss 162–165.

²⁴¹ Gambia News, 'President Jammeh Gives Ultimatum for Homosexuals to Leave' (19 May 2008, archived 15 March 2012, retrieved 13 May 2024)

²⁴² Michelle Nichols, 'Gambian President Says Gays a Threat to Human Existence' Reuters (28 September 2013).

banning homosexual acts.²⁴³ In 1997, a court found Canaan Banana, Mugabe's predecessor and the first President of Zimbabwe, guilty of 11 counts of sodomy and indecent assault. Mugabe has previously referred to LGBT people as being "worse than dogs and pigs"²⁴⁴

In an effort to counteract the emergence of homosexuality and *LGBTQ* tendencies within its jurisdiction, the Parliament of Ghana recently introduced a highly controversial bill aimed at criminalising LGBTQ activities and penalising anyone who supports them²⁴⁵. This move follows similar legislative actions taken by Kenya and Uganda, Tanzania Chad etc. which have also enacted stringent anti-LGBTQ laws.

The new bill, presented by the Ghanaian parliament has been widely criticised and described as draconian and harsh due to its alleged violations of several human rights. Critics argue that the bill's measures are excessive, as it not only targets homosexual individuals but also punishes those who provide support or advocacy for LGBTQ rights²⁴⁶.

The international community has responded to the legislative actions against LGBTQ rights in African countries with varying degrees of condemnation and concern²⁴⁷. Human rights organisations, such as Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch, have been vocal in criticising this bill for violating fundamental human rights, including the rights to privacy, freedom of expression, and freedom from discrimination. These organisations argue that such legislation is inherently discriminatory and undermines the basic principles of human dignity and equality. This strong opposition to homosexuality across Africa highlights the continent's fundamental commitment to its cultural, religious, and social values. Many African societies view homosexuality as a direct contradiction to their traditional beliefs and religious teachings²⁴⁸.

Contrary to this, homosexuality is widely accepted in many Western cultures, a shift that the authors find puzzling. This acceptance seems paradoxical given that it was Western missionaries

²⁴³ Zimbabwe, Criminal Law (Codification and Reform) Act 2004 (effective 2006).

²⁴⁴ Christopher Brocklebank, 'Police Raid Headquarters of LGBT Rights Group' PinkNews (14 August 2012).

²⁴⁵ Al Jazeera, 'Ghana's Parliament Passes Anti-LGBTQ Bill' (28 February 2024) <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2024/2/28/ghanas-parliament-passes-anti-lgbtq-bill>

²⁴⁶ 76Crimes, 'Ghana's Harsh Anti-LGBTQ Bill Is Back' (7 March 2025) <https://76crimes.com/2025/03/07/ghanas-harsh-anti-lgbtq-bill-is-back/>

²⁴⁷ Amnesty International, 'Africa: Barrage of Discriminatory Laws Stoking Hate Against LGBTI Persons' (January 2024) <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2024/01/africa-barrage-of-discriminatory-laws-stoking-hate-against-lgbti-persons/>.

²⁴⁸ Sylvia Tamale, 'Confronting the Politics of Nonconforming Sexualities in Africa' (2013) 56(2) African Studies Review 31.

who introduced Christianity to Africa, teaching that homosexuality is wrong, as exemplified in the biblical story of Sodom and Gomorrah²⁴⁹. From the perspective of the authors, it appears hypocritical for Western societies to now embrace homosexuality while African nations, adhering to the same religious teachings introduced by the West, are condemned for their opposition.

This situation raises critical questions about the evolution of Western values and the perceived abandonment of traditional Christian teachings. It appears to the authors that the West, which once propagated strict Christian moral codes, is now moving away from those teachings in favor of their secular and carnal instincts. This shift could be interpreted as the West prioritising individual freedoms and whimsical carnal convictions over traditional religious doctrines.

Furthermore, the authors question whether this trend represents a broader abandonment of long-held virtues and beliefs to satisfy contemporary social and political agendas. They ponder whether Western societies are selectively interpreting religious teachings to align with modern trends, or if they are outright disregarding religious doctrines in favor of personal autonomy and carnal satisfaction.

The divergent approaches to homosexuality between African and Western countries reflect deep cultural, religious, and ideological divides. While African nations maintain their opposition based on traditional values and religious beliefs, Western countries advocate for LGBTQ rights as part of a broader commitment to individual freedoms. This ongoing debate underscores the complexities of navigating cultural differences in a globalised world and highlights the challenges of promoting universal human rights in diverse cultural contexts.

CONCLUSION

The authors contend that homosexuality is not a recent phenomenon but rather a deviation from societal norms that has been documented since the earliest records of civilised human history. While this phenomenon has historically faced widespread rejection across various cultures, there has been a notable shift in recent times toward greater acceptance of homosexual behavior globally. The authors attribute this shift, in part, to the declining influence of religion in certain

²⁴⁹ Genesis 18–19 (Biblical account of Sodom and Gomorrah, often cited in relation to sodomy laws).

regions, a trend supported by statistical data and empirical evidence presented throughout this paper.

Furthermore, the authors argue that the question of whether homosexuality should be permitted or prohibited remains a matter of public and national policy. However, based on the evidence examined, there is no conclusive scientific proof to suggest that homosexuality or other non-normative sexual behaviors originate from inherent biological traits. Instead, research indicates that such behaviors are more likely influenced by environmental, cultural, or psychological factors. This paper emphasises the nuanced nature of the topic and advocates for a delicate and considered approach in addressing it.

The authors highlight that the primary basis for labeling homosexuality as "unnatural" stems from religious frameworks, which are not universally adhered to. Consequently, imposing religious dogma on individuals who do not share such beliefs is deemed irrational. While a range of laws pertaining to freedom of expression and sexuality appear to support the acceptance of homosexuality, other legal frameworks continue to categorise it as unnatural. Given the divergent legal stances across jurisdictions, the authors assert that the determination of whether homosexuality is natural and should be permitted should be left to the discretion of individual jurisdictions, reflecting their unique cultural, social, and legal contexts.

